

Book of abstracts

Citizen Science for Health conference
29 Oct – 1 Nov 2023

University of Twente, Enschede
The Netherlands

Monday, October 30 (11:15-12:45)

Solution rooms I; 20 minutes (session 1-3)

1 - How to measure impact on participants' learning in citizen science projects?

Petra Havinga, Imke Herms

Room TL2107 (TMC)

Background. Many high school students with mental health problems struggle with the dilemma whether or not to disclose these problems at post-secondary education. On the one hand, there is the fear of being excluded or stigmatized. On the other hand, hiding the problems can get in the way of receiving support. The 'To tell or not to tell?'-intervention offers support with the disclosure dilemma to students in order to come to a well-informed decision. We plan to implement and evaluate the 'To tell or not to tell?'-intervention within secondary education schools. This project involves equal collaboration between a former student who experienced the disclosure-dilemma and a researcher (shared leadership). High school students will also be actively involved. Challenge. The challenge we run into is how to measure projects impact on individual learning outcomes of the participants in this projects. The aim of this session is to gain insight into how others dealt with this challenge. Specifically, the following topics will be discussed: (i) how to determine the intended learning outcomes? and, (ii) which instruments/tools are recommended to measure individual learning outcomes? The session starts with a brief explanation of the challenge. Then participants get time to think and write down their thoughts. Finally, answers will be reviewed in a plenary discussion.

2 - The Challenges of Impact Assessment in Citizen Science Health Studies

Teresa Schaefer, Claudia M. Fabian, Barbara Kieslinger

Room TL2187 (TMC)

If individual citizens are actively involved in health studies, how can we best assess the impact of this involvement that goes beyond personal health insights? We see several evaluation indicators and instruments being developed and applied by the citizen science community which investigate the impact of citizen science activities on those citizens actively involved, such as personal learning or behavioral change. But the health domain is very sensible and involving citizens in research must thoroughly thought through with e.g., regard to privacy issues and ethical considerations. This is also true when we want to learn about the intended and unintended consequences that citizen scientists have from their involvement in a citizen science health study. Disciplinary views on how to implement health studies may differ a lot in this sense and may contradict with the active engagement of citizens at points. In the InChildHealth project (www.inchildhealth.eu) we involve children at the age from 6 to 12 years and their parents across Europe in our health study related to indoor air quality and health effects. We have developed several instruments to learn about the impact of this involvement, specifically adjusted to the health domain. If you want to hear about the challenges, which we are having in implementing a scientifically sound process that respects interdisciplinary requirements, and share your experiences, join this solution room. We will start the session with a brainwalk and then discuss the shared experiences together.

3 - Identifying Opportunities for Funders to Promote the Use of Citizen Science in Health Research

Jennifer Couch, Ellen Mintz

Room TL2389 (TMC)

Funders of health research and biomedical science face unique challenges in supporting innovative research methods that include citizen science, community science, and patient or community-led research. Support mechanisms designed for traditional academic research teams often do not align well with patient- and community-led projects. Evaluation metrics, data access and sharing, and fluctuating priorities all affect funding opportunities. Methods that successfully support citizen science and community-engaged research in other disciplines may not translate effectively to citizen science for health due to challenges including privacy concerns, community trust, and healthcare accessibility differences. Yet despite these challenges, funders of biomedical science and health research have found creative ways to partner with the public to accomplish research. Research in the health and biomedical sciences span basic biology, clinical and epidemiological research, and the impact of health disparities and the environment. Members of the public have been engaged in contributing data, insights and observations as well as finding creative solutions to problems and contributing directly to data analysis through platforms and games. This solution room will bring together policy makers and funders to share challenges and their successful strategies for promoting the use of citizen science in health research, learn from and expand upon traditional research approaches, and share strategies for adapting technologies and approaches to support local, national, and international biomedical science and health research.

Workshops I; 90 minutes (session 4-8)

4 - Guidelines and oversight: developing a framework for ethical citizen science for health

Nienke Beerlage-De Jong, Adam Henschke, Jodi Sturge, Ria Wolkorte

Room TL1336 (TMC)

Citizen science is a novel approach to impactful health research. The value of engaging citizens in research through research design, data collection and dissemination is recognized by a mix of disciplines and funders. Despite the motivation to conduct citizen science in health, how it works in practice still needs to be discovered. Further, several emerging and critical ethical issues must be considered when conducting citizen science for health. Institutional Review Boards (IRBs) receive more applications for citizen science projects. Yet, the standard forms and procedures do not capture the dynamics or risks of conducting citizen science research for health. This workshop aims to explore the challenges faced by IRBs in Citizen Science for Health Research, and to propose ways that IRBs need to evolve to meet changes offered by citizen science. The workshop will be hosted by an interdisciplinary team of researchers with backgrounds in psychology, health sciences, philosophy, ethics, and design, dealing with citizen science as researchers and/or as members of IRBs. This interdisciplinary team of researchers brings a diverse, international experience to citizen science. We will share our efforts towards practical guidance for ethical overview of citizen science for health projects at the University of Twente. Further, we will explore ethical issues and challenges that can emerge in citizen science, such as the dual roles of citizens, oversight of the collaborative process, expectation management, rapport, data management, GDPR, privacy and ownership. In doing so, we draw from our personal experiences as researchers and IRB-members in citizen science for health projects to reflect on current and proposed procedures that are in place at the University of Twente, but also on a recently executed literature review and a subsequent survey among IRBs on the topic. Based on our work, we are working towards the development of a framework of recommendations, guidelines and training to support researchers and IRBs to understand and mitigate the risks of engaging citizens in scientific research. An initial set-up of such framework will be presented during the workshop. Through active discussions with participants about specific aspects of ethical oversight through IRBs, participants are given the opportunity to actively help shape the future of ethical oversight for Citizen Science for health. This way, via a collective effort, we are hoping to eventually present a framework that is thought provoking, yet supportive rather than restrictive, for those executing or ethically reviewing citizen science for health projects. This workshop is for researchers, members of the ethics committee and citizens interested in citizen science. Participants will learn how ethical oversight for citizen science for health projects is currently organized at the University of Twente and how the IRB of the UT is exploring ways to adapt their oversight procedures for CS4H projects specifically.

5 - Applying the ‘vision in design’ methodology in technology development with and for people in vulnerable health positions

Julia van Calis, Hanneke van Heijster, Emilie Tromp, Meike Theunnissen

Room TL2148 (TMC)

Theme: Research methods and toolkits (apps, e-health devices) to conduct CS research in the health domain. Methods: The ‘vision in design’ methodology is a form of design thinking for innovative technology development. The method can be categorized into three steps, namely 1) mapping the needs and interests of the target group and their current and future context 2) formulating desired interactions between target group and technology, i.e. what are the desired experiences for the target group, and 3) designing the product, i.e., how can technological innovations contribute to accomplish the desired experiences. The vision in design methodology centralizes the needs and interests of the target group in the development of the technological innovation. The method is also used to involve citizens during the design process.

Content of the workshop: During the workshop we will take participants through the first step of the vision in design methodology, namely mapping the needs of the target group and their current and future context. We will focus on a case in which a sensitive chatbot technology is developed for people with disabilities and/or (chronic) mental health issues, who need care and support (e.g., medical care, psychological and social care) in their daily lives. These ‘vulnerable care recipients’ often face difficulties in finding and accessing this care and support. We will show how needs and interests of this vulnerable and diverse target group are based on the Ford and Nichols’ Taxonomy of Human Goals (1987), resulting in ‘needs and interests profiles’ for the target group. Also, we will explain the role of three citizen scientists in this process. Our own experiences will serve as an example during the workshop to guide the participants through the process. This will give participants insight into how to apply this open and bottom-up approach for a vulnerable group of technology users.

Potential benefits for participants: Participants will get acquainted with a design methodology that can be used in citizen science research. We will provide guidelines on how the participants can identify the needs and interests of a vulnerable and diverse target group when developing a technological innovation. This provides a solid basis for a well-founded development process and can be used to fall back on during further development.

6 - The games we play: Exploring implicit processes in collaboration through arts-based methods

Marieke Breed, Nienke Slagboom, Matty Crone, Sanne de Vries

Room Inform (DL)

Collaboration is at the heart of community-based health studies. After all, community-based health approaches require an approach that synchronizes the efforts of citizens, clinicians, public health officials and policymakers. However, collaboration can be more difficult than it seems. The implementation of community-based approaches can be hampered by complexities in collaboration. But how can we study implicit processes that hinder or facilitate community-based health approaches? In our community-based study, we focus on co-designing a community resilience approach to improve health and wellbeing in two cities in the Netherlands. As part of this study, we aim to understand the explicit as well as the implicit processes that facilitate and hinder collaboration between citizens and professionals. In doing so, we noticed that implicit processes -often very powerful- are difficult to capture in words. Traditional research methods may struggle to capture these implicit processes, leading to a potential gap in our understanding of the intricacies involved in effective community-based participative health research. This workshop aims to shed light on the study of implicit processes within the realm of collaboration by employing arts-based methods as a means of exploration and analysis. Throughout this workshop, participants will be introduced to a variety of arts-based and arts-informed techniques and tools that can be utilized to explore implicit processes in collaboration. In the first part of the workshop, we will share how we have employed theater improvisation, metaphors, drawings and building blocks to analyze collaboration processes in community-based participative health studies. In the second part of the workshop, participants are invited to experiment with these methods, fostering a hands-on and experiential learning environment. By engaging in arts-based methods, participants can explore collaboration processes in their own citizen science projects. We would also like to learn from others who have bridged the world of art and collaboration research, participants will be encouraged to share their methods and experiences. The workshop is designed for researchers and practitioners interested in deepening their understanding of collaboration processes. We hope to sensitize the participants for both arts -based and arts- informed methods and the implicit processes in 'the games we play'.

7 - Active Living at your workplace: How to get started!

Linnea Marie Sjöberg, Ezra Lodder, Tina Dalager

Room Learn-X (DL)

Method and content of the workshop A tentative plan for the workshop:

- 1) Introduction: Why should we integrate more movement during work hours? (5 minutes)
- 2) Two inspiring cases: SDU Moves (10 minutes) and VU in Motion 10 minutes)
- 3) Involving participants: What would you recommend when integrating more movement at your workplace? Where do you see the barriers, and where is the potential for co-creation with the employees (2x20 minutes in different groups)
- 4) Top 3 recommendations and cultural changes: Discussion among the participants about the three best voted recommendations and how to involve citizens in making changes (20 minutes)
- 5) Outro: Participants can comment on the take-aways from the workshop (5 minutes)

Potential benefits for participants We will conduct an engaging and active workshop, where participants can share their ideas, experience, and thoughts on working with behavioral change and culture to achieve an active living at the workplace. Attendees can also share their thoughts and ideas on the concrete findings and methods within the two presented projects. As concrete take-aways the participants will get recommendations on how to integrate movement at their workplace and during their own workday.

SDU Moves 'SDU Moves' is a strategy at University of Southern Denmark's (SDU) working with the UN Sustainability Development Goals since fall 2020. SDU Moves focus on SDG 3, Health and Well-being, by aiming to empower staff to enhance movement during their workday through a Citizen Science co-creation method. Through repetitive activities, events, and workshops SDU Moves inspires and motivates employees – our citizens – to a behavioral change. By now the SDU Moves project has documented that 5.778 employees have participated in movement activities, and in addition to that, employees have also been active on their own for example having walking meetings. We conducted a baseline survey for all employees at SDU in November 2020 where the citizens could elaborate what expectations and wishes they had for the project. The citizens thoughts and ideas were followed up each year by a new survey. The last survey will be sent out in November 2023.

VU in Motion 'VU in Motion' is a project that aims to make the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam the most 'moveable' university of the Netherlands. More important, however, is the hidden aim to alter the sedentary culture that is present at the university. VU in Motion has launched five projects, ranging from 'movement breaks' in the lecture halls to free Salsa and Tai-Chi on the Campus square, to bring movement to the forefront of academic life. More projects, initiated by our network of 'movement enthusiasts', are set to commence in September. VU in Motion is currently in the process of transferring the five initial projects into the wider organization, thereby ensuring continuity.

8 - Patient-driven research communities in health: mapping international bottom-up approaches

Gaston Remmers, Martijn de Groot, Sara Riggare, Ilona Wilmont

Room Invite (DL)

Patients are keen observers of their own health and some of them develop quite structured approaches to map their own experiences and experiments. Internationally, these are known under labels such as Do-it-Yourself medicine (Wexler, 2022) or Personal Science (Wolf and Groot, 2020). They share their insights via a diversity of communities and fora. At the same time they tend to be not very strongly organized between them. Lots of potentially rich citizen science in the health domain hence remains under the radar. Their relative invisibility hampers the development of conditions that would increase the value of their work such as methodology, ethics, funding, publications, data-infrastructure and recognition. In The Netherlands for example, there are at least 10 of these patient communities, linked to a diversity of health conditions such as heart failure, cancer, epilepsy, diabetes, rare diseases etc. Together they constitute at least 10.000 people engaged in some sort of bottom-up citizen science. They have recently organized themselves as a Dutch network of self-researching communities, operating as a platform for Citizen Science on health (called ZONN). Internationally, the Quantified Self community has generated hundreds of powerful examples of Personal Science projects (<https://quantifiedself.com/show-and-tell/>). There is one case of a patient advocate who even successfully defended a PhD thesis based on self-tracking (Riggare, 2022). This workshop aims to create room for an international exchange between patient and citizen communities that conduct or develop forms of citizen science, and that want to learn from each other. The workshop will kick-off with a short 5 min introduction and 3 pitches of 5 minutes each that provide an idea of the diversity of self-researching communities. We invite other communities (national and international) to join the conversation, and to deliver a short pitch of their work in patient-driven Citizen Science in health. The workshop contains an interactive part to explore the strengths and challenges of these patient-driven research initiatives & communities. The workshop aims to build and publish a concise white paper to enhance visibility of patient-driven and conducted research. Patient communities across the globe interested in delivering a short pitch in this workshop are kindly requested to send a short summary of their pitch to the organizer of the workshop (max 500 words).

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Solution rooms II; 20 minutes (session 9-13)

9 - Taking the next step: How to face the challenges of moving towards Citizen Science?

Eline te Braake, Kira Oberschmidt, Marian Hurmuz, Stephanie Jansen-Kosterink, Christiane Grünloh
Room TL2107 (TMC)

Within the RE-SAMPLE project (Horizon grant no. 965315) we created a patient panel for participatory design. Within this panel, interested participants can think along and participate in our studies. Like most panels, those participating are often highly motivated to participate in research and live a healthy life, have a high social economic position (SEP), and have high (health/technology) literacy. During sessions, we often hear that participants like our ideas but would not benefit from it themselves. They do not need additional support because they can manage their conditions on their own. However, they all can imagine 'others' who might benefit greatly from such support, implying the lack of representativeness within the panel. As we have quite some experiences with participatory design, we are very interested in taking the next step: moving towards a panel of engaged co-researchers. We are aware of the many difficulties that might come with taking those first steps. However, we would like to hear about how others face these difficulties (e.g., how to create a safe space for co-researchers, how to deal with time constraints). Besides, if we want to take a shift within this panel, we also move the problem of representativeness which might eventually negatively affect projects and research initiatives. Therefore, we also wonder how we can reach those people who are difficult to reach. Hence, we aim to discuss two questions during our solution room:

- 1) How to reach the difficult to reach people?
- 2) How to move towards a panel of co-researchers?

10 - Effective communication about health among a various group of stakeholders: language use, power relations, and vulnerability

Maud ter Bogt
Room TL2187 (TMC)

Theme/question addressed: Our health is influenced by many people and our environment. Collaborations between citizens and professionals from various domains is becoming more popular. Yet, communication barriers are experienced. What is

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needed to communicate effectively with a various group of stakeholders including citizens, municipality policy advisors and care professionals? Aim of the session: This solution room aims to gain insights into how a various group of stakeholders can communicate effectively about health with regard to language use, power relations, and vulnerability. Intended methods: During the session a knowledge carousel will be used. Content of the solution rooms: During the session we will use focus on three different communication aspects: 1) language use; 2) power relations and 3) communicating with regard to vulnerability (e.g. personal circumstances). Therefore, three carousel stands will be created. In round one (8 minutes) the group is split into three subgroups. Every subgroup will discuss one of the three communication aspects, and draw or write insights at the stand. In round two (5 minutes) every participant choses their communication aspect of interest and joins that carousel stand to discuss the topic, and draw or write insights at the stand. In the third round (6 minutes), gained insights are shared plenary.

11 - Citizen science to break the deadlock of 'traditional' patient involvement

Carina Pittens, Sevgi Fruytier

Room TL2389 (TMC)

Since the 1990s, a call is made for a more active and prominent role for patients in health decision-making processes in order to make the health system more responsive to patients' needs. As a result, numerous efforts are nowadays visible and patients are increasingly seen as partners.

Despite the great attention to and the many initiatives on patient involvement, involvement remains an add-on to the traditional health system, mainly involving a slight adaptation of structures and practices. Such initiatives remain often disconnected from actual decision-making processes and are thus more or less insignificant.

How to overcome the perceived difficulties? We hypothesize that use of creativity and flexibility – outside the boundaries of what we consider familiar and standard - is essential to realize a meaningful change. Radical experimentation is needed to help break the current deadlock in the field of patient involvement.

In this solution room, we would like to get inspired by the successes of citizen science and fed with ideas for radical experimentation with more needs-responsive health research and care outside the boundaries of the current health system and closer to those who experience health issues (citizens, patients). After introducing the problem with examples of system barriers, we invite participants to share their successes and ideas using creative formats (drawing, writing). We will collectively discuss the input and how it can break the deadlock.

12 - A science of engagement in health research and innovation: New roles for citizen scientists as peer researchers who bring a new patient research voice to health transformation.

Nancy Marlett

Room TL1251 (TMC)

Themes: • Reaching CS Engagement goals for academic and community health research • Drivers of health research transformation: social innovation and community based health alternatives, commercialization of health technologies and social enterprise models and the need to reform and democratize science to keep pace with rapid global environmental and political challenges to health, rising costs and crises in social determinants of health. • Communities of Practice for health researchers who are interested in exploring new, qualitative, and participatory research models to engage patients in research and innovation. • Training patients and community members to conduct peer research as part of academic and health care research teams using methods co designed and tested to engage patients and communities in pragmatic research. Intended methods: • Explore resources about patient engagement platforms and programs with leaders in national initiatives in patient engagement in research and local innovative programs. • Group work to locate workshop participant positions in established CS engagement models in the current landscape of health research. • Introduce elements of peer research: patient researcher roles, new and adapted methods, adapted and new theories and bridges to innovation as part of co design in research projects. • Explore the science of engagement using case studies and reports to explore to new patient roles in citizen science. Questions: a. Answer the short survey about the research priorities you anticipate for the future of health care and the research needed to prepare for the changes. b. In working groups, identify yourself in engagement models proposed by CS and Community Health Research. c. Locate your goal for engaging patients and the obstacles you anticipate in reaching this goal. d. Identify where you are on concept maps using stickers identify your goal for patient engagement in your research i. Learn more about the landscape of democratizing science platforms ii. Forces driving health care transformation iii. Engagement Strategies iv. Co design of quantitative methods for peer research combining Participatory Action research, Narrative Data and Grounded theory iterative cycles of constant comparison and planning next steps. e. Choose a group to discuss how to learn more about SoE. Benefits: • Participants learn about models of engagement in health research that align with citizen science. • Explore a science of engagement that support new relationships with citizens who want to learn how to conduct research in underserved and marginalized groups as part of academic and community research teams. • Understand new approaches that build on citizen / patient ways of knowing and sharing information that can build bridges between research, practice, innovation and publication. • The advantages of

blending existing research methods to use participatory principles, narrative data science and grounded theory constant comparison to guide inductive, responsive methods to make a difference. • Ways to engage groups facing systemic and structural discrimination through research designed to promote Justice, Equity, Diversity and Inclusion.

13 - Establishing a global typology for citizen engagement in health research

Ingrid Nielssen, Sandra Zelinsky, Sadia Ahmed, Paul Fairie, Maria Santana

Room Invite (DL)

'Citizen science for health research' encompasses a broad range of approaches and terminology that describe research collaborations between essential and multidisciplinary stakeholders. Distinguishing similarities and nuanced differences between, and within, collaborations globally is challenging without consensus in language and context of application. The variousness in language about methodologies and players leads to confusion and obfuscates collective, continued learning and more meaningful international collaboration. A co-developed typology is an imperative to be able to better discuss and share learnings, avoid duplication, and increase opportunities to advance this essential science. The solution room will seek to have participants describe the different ways organizations in their home countries engage patient, public and community members in health research, the participatory approaches used as well as the way co-produced evidence becomes used to inform health care policy and practice improvement. The hope is to use large Post-It notes to have participants identify, then subsequently sort, key funding organizations (i.e. CIHR, NIHR, PCORI, etc.) in their home countries; the unique purposes of research collaborations (i.e. to produce research evidence, to advise on policy and practice improvement, etc.); and to clarify the language used to describe the various stakeholders, their roles and the relationships between them. Participants will also be encouraged to share useful links to websites that can offer further description or elaboration. The Alberta SPOR SUPPORT Unit (AbSPORU) Patient Engagement Team will then synthesize and share back the results.

Showcases I; 20 minutes (session 14-16)

14 - Optimizing the Wisdom of the Crowd for Classification Tasks

Pietro Michelucci

Room Inform (DL)

"Wisdom of the crowd" approaches combine answers from many non-experts into a single expertlike answer. To increase analytic throughput in citizen science platforms, the Human Computation Institute has developed wisdom of crowd algorithms that are theoretically optimal under certain assumptions. These methods have enabled a five-fold improvement in the speed at which the Stall Catchers project analyzes Alzheimer's disease research data. This has reduced the research time from decades to just a few years, resulting in over three million crowd-generated annotations, which have enabled research findings published in Nature, PLOS One, and Brain. We will, for the first time, reveal the details of these methods and demonstrate how they are applied to crowdsourced classification tasks to minimize the required number of non-expert contributions while maintaining target accuracy.

15 - The OIS Impact Model: Planning and assessing the impact of co-creation in research

Matthieu Mahve-Beydokhti

Room Learn-X (DL)

The co-creatively developed OIS (Open Innovation in Science) Impact Model shows what effects cocreation activities and initiatives in research could have on personal awareness and competencies, behavior and life circumstances of all those involved. The change elements of the OIS Impact Model display definitions and stakeholders that are affected by each element. They are filled with examples of how the different change elements can be assessed. The model can be used as a planning tool: research teams can identify the key change elements they aspire to influence with their participatory initiative and set up appropriate assessment mechanisms throughout and at the end of the research project. The OIS Impact Model is presented as a downloadable toolkit folder and as an interactive map. During this showcase, the OIS Impact Model will be demonstrated, and participants will be able to test the interactive map.

16 - Framework for active involvement in participatory eHealth research

Kira Oberschmidt, Christiane Grünloh, Monique Tabak

Room Inspire (DL)

Stakeholder involvement throughout the research process is central to citizen science in healthcare and eHealth research. We developed a framework to help researchers shape the active involvement of stakeholders in their projects. The

framework is based on the principles of Action Research and is applicable to other participatory approaches, like citizen science. The development took place in a large-scale European project with several pilots all working on active and healthy ageing. The evaluation of the framework also took place in other research projects and with experts in participatory approaches. The framework includes pointer questions for different phases of iterative research involving stakeholders and can be easily implemented in any participatory healthcare project. The showcase will include the digital version of this framework, which can be openly accessed via a website. Therefore, to best present the showcase, a computer / screen, or electricity to plug in a laptop would be needed.

Monday, October 30 (14:30-14:50)

Showcases II; 20 minutes (session 17-19)

17 - A showcase for Science of Engagement (SoE) in health research and innovation as part of Citizen Science, Community Health Research and Patient Engagement Research platforms.

Nancy Marlett

Room Inform (DL)

SoE is a book supporting peer research done by patients and community members trained to engage unheard voices in health care, planning, research, and policy. It supports a conference venue celebrating international patient engagement platforms or a plenary panel. North America, Europe, UK and Australia have dedicated policy and funding to support engaging patients in health research that would be invited to participate and plan the event. Topics would include the roles patients enact in research (using Citizen Science engagement models), training provided for patients and researchers, project examples of patient involvement in publications and healthcare transformation planning groups. This inaugural CS4H conference provides a unique venue for those working in CS and Patient Engagement spaces to work together during the conference as an opportunity to facilitate peer research as a foundation to address JEDI concerns and build a framework for patient input into technology development and healthcare transformation.

18 - Patient and Community Engagement Research (PaCER)- an experiential based, participatory health research methodology program

Ingrid Nielsens, Sandra Zelinsky, Sadia Ahmed, Paul Fairie, Maria Santana

Room TL2148 (TMC)

The Patient and Community Engagement Research (PaCER) program is a one year, online experiential based learning program offered through the University of Calgary, Continuing Education in partnership with the Alberta SPOR SUPPORT Unit, (AbSPORU) Patient Engagement Team. Teams of seven diverse community and patient learners are sponsored by research teams, health organizations, patient and community organizations and others. Over three courses, learners gain an understanding of participatory health research methodology and then design, develop, and conduct a patient-led qualitative study about a health topic or challenge that matters to them. Evidence from the peer-to-peer projects can inform future research priorities; feed into larger research projects; and inform change to health care policy and practice. The presentation will highlight the PaCER approach, program delivery and some previous projects. This presentation will require access to support sharing a Powerpoint presentation.

19 - "CoAct for Mental Health" Chatbot: a practical demonstration of a "humans to humans" chatbot reinterpreted for citizen social science

Isabelle Bonhoure, Assumpta Mateu, Amanda Figueras

Room Learn-X (DL)

The "CoAct for Mental Health" chatbot is a Telegram mobile-based messaging tool to send the microstories written by the Co-Researchers to the Citizen Scientists. Citizen Scientists can answer using buttons and in a structured manner over a long period of time, once or twice every day. The chatbot source code is openly accessible in Creative Commons licence in a Github repository. The chatbot functioning will be showcased in real time by 2 CoResearchers and a member of the promoting team, thus introducing this innovative tool to the conference participants. Using a chatbot for health participatory research has several benefits: the participants can answer the question when it is most convenient for them, thus integrating participation into their daily routines. They can also answer in a private manner and in safe surroundings. The chatbot is also seen as a medium to explore how to increase long-term engagement, which is particularly challenging in Citizen Science projects.

Solution rooms III; 20 minutes (session 20-23)

20 - How to measure impact of citizen science in public health projects?

Saskia te Velde, Rhoda Schuling, Berry van Holland

Room Play (DL)

Citizen science projects in the public health domain are complex in nature. They affect several aspects of personal health and cover a wide variety of outcomes. Think of, for example, heart patients undergoing surgery and monitoring their recovery by tracking physical activity, nutrition, and rehabilitation. Another example is residents collaborating in creating healthier living environments. Both are examples of citizen science, but with completely different target groups and outcomes. The impact that is accomplished within these projects is not always well-defined beforehand and also hard to grasp afterwards. The question also arises how long you should continue measuring impact. Moreover, is the impact over time still attributable to the citizen science process? In this solution room, we want to dive into the issues and use our combined knowledge to move forward. Questions we want to address in this solution room are: - What impact do we want to realize by using citizen science? - How can we measure the desired impact? - Which tools are available to measure impact? We want to set the first steps towards standardization in measuring impact in citizen science projects aimed at public health. The input will be gathered in three short phases: thinking individually, sharing in pairs, and exchanging in the group. Desired outcomes of the session are conditions for standardization.

21 - Community engagement during the COVID-19 crisis: what can we learn from this?

Annemarie Wagemakers, Lea den Broeder

Room TL2107 (TMC)

Background: During the COVID-19 crisis, a varied number of health promoting activities have been organized to engage citizens, including citizens in a vulnerable position. Examples include online music lessons, neighborhood meals, Balcony Fit and online platforms for mutual help. These activities enable citizens, communities and organizations to build resilience and community power. Important features of community actions include increase in mutual aid and neighborhood ties, the central role of community based organizations, changing patterns of volunteering, use of digital media and health promotion opportunities. How could these actions feed into collective research activity?

Aim of the session: In this solution room, we aim to explore how to learn from the lessons and experiences gained during the COVID-19 crisis. Participants are invited to express and share their experiences and views about how to promote community engagement for health promotion research. Participants will gain tips on how to engage communities, also not in times of crisis.

Program of the solution room: In this solution room, we will use 'talking with the feet' to guide the discussion. Talking with the feet is a democratic tool that invites all participants to participate and express their opinion. This encourages people to be active and visualize their positions. We will ask participants questions about community engagement in research starting from lessons learned during COVID.

22 - cancelled

23 - Participatory research into clown visits in long-term care: How to better engage persons with dementia in the research process?

Lieke de Kock, Charlotte Langemeijer, Barbara Groot, Silvia de Feveri

Room TL1251 (TMC)

There is a growing interest worldwide in the potential of clowns working in long term dementia care settings. Research has shown that clowns can have a positive influence on the wellbeing of residents with dementia. The impact clown play can have on quality of life largely depends on the context in which the intervention takes place. The way collaboration takes place on the work floor between clowns, residents, care staff and family members, seems to have a great influence on the effect of the intervention. In a three-country participatory action research project led by Leyden Academy on Vitality and Ageing, cofunded by Creative Europe, we addressed the question: How does the context of a long-term care facility affect the impact of clown play on the quality of life of residents with dementia, and how may we improve working relations between clown organisations and long-term care facilities? In this solution room we will briefly present the findings from the research projects in The Netherlands, Austria and Germany. We noticed that by reflecting together with all stakeholders, mutual understanding about relational care emerged. We worked closely together with clowns, care staff, wellbeing staff, management and family members. However, we were unable to sufficiently involve persons with dementia themselves in the process. We would like to share our thinking since, and hear from other participants about creative and innovative ways of involving persons with dementia as citizens in follow-up research projects.

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Workshops II; 90 minutes (session 24-28, 52)

24 - Digital Storytelling (DST) in Health Research

Sandra Zelinsky, Sadia Ahmed, Paul Fairie, Maria Santana

Room TL1336 (TMC)

Stories and storytelling help us to make sense of our thoughts, feelings, and experiences. They help us to better understand our environment, interactions with others and to formulate and convey our values, beliefs and insights for ourselves and others.

Digital Storytelling (DST) in research can be used as an innovative Community-Based Participatory Research (CBPR) method that increases the involvement of people with lived experience in health research. Digital stories are short (3-5 minutes), first person video narratives created with the combination of images, video, narration, and music. DST has been used by academics across disciplines, including health research for the past two decades. In this workshop, we will focus on DST methods, how DST works in practice as well as its benefits and challenges to health research. This workshop will introduce you to a 7-step methodology developed by Story Center, US (Lambert, J., 2020, Digital Storytelling: Story Work for Urgent Time, Berkeley, CA.: Digital Diner Press). The 7-steps include owning your insights, owning your emotions, finding the moment, seeing your story, hearing your story, assembling your story, and sharing your story. As a CBPR method, DST can help to reach and elevate the voices of underrepresented populations and can be used as a tool to meaningfully engage populations who value storytelling as a way of knowing and understanding. It could potentially be used as a tool to personalize quantitative data, understand what matters most to patients and as a powerful knowledge translation tool.

The workshop outline:

1. Introduction to digital storytelling as a methodology: including the 7-steps involved to develop a digital story.
2. View and discuss the use of digital stories in health research. What are the benefits and considerations of this arts-based approach?

Group discussion on ethical considerations when using DST in health research.

25 - Mapping accessibility of the UT campus for people with disabilities

Johannes Flacke, Karin Pfeffer, Heike Koeckler, Julia Brueggemann, Christian Walter Klose

Room TL2148 (TMC)

The design of accessible and walkable public spaces requires the participation of citizens with diverse abilities to capture their specific demands as a basis for promoting healthy active living for all. However, public spaces are often designed for average-abled people neglecting the diverse needs of people with various disabilities. Moreover, no concepts and methods exist to include people with disabilities in the inclusive design of urban public spaces. The workshop will demonstrate methods and approaches developed in two citizen science projects on co-designing accessible public spaces for and with people with disabilities. In the projects, two groups of people with disabilities, a group with physical disabilities from the Netherlands and a group with cognitive disabilities from Germany, co-designed together with the team of researchers an approach to design inclusive public spaces and an inclusive participatory mapping tool implemented on an interactive touchscreen (mactable). Methods explored in the projects comprise photovoice, metal maps, photorealistic 3D visualization, and participatory mapping. The goal of the workshop is to demonstrate a) what barriers people with disabilities experience with respect to accessibility to public spaces, b) how such barriers can be mapped, and c) how people with disabilities can contribute to the inclusive design of public spaces. The workshop will let the participants experience hands-on the entire methodology as developed in the projects. The first half of the workshop will be used to capture barriers to accessibility for people with disabilities in the UT campus area by applying photovoice methods and photorealistic 3D visualization. In the second half of the workshop participants will do participatory mapping of accessibility to public spaces with the inclusive collaborative mapping tool. Citizen science researchers from both project case studies will join the workshop, demonstrate the use of the tools, and explain their usefulness. From the workshop participants learn about limitations in accessibility to public spaces for people with disabilities, challenges related to the cross-disability perspective, and the added value of tool co-design. We will bring all the technical equipment needed for the workshop (mactable, set of tablets). Required are two tables, good internet accessibility, a room with different corners or three smaller rooms where people can experiment with the different methods.

26 - Citizen Science for Health: Exploring Stakeholders' Different Perspectives

Jacqueline Maschino, Jolanda Huizer, Sanne Steenhuisen

Room Learn-X (DL)

Participation is not a new concept. ZonMw has been embracing it since its inception. We actively involve patients, individuals with lived experiences, healthcare providers, and other stakeholders in many of our projects. We firmly believe that engaging diverse perspectives improves the quality and relevance of the knowledge we co-create, ultimately increasing its impact. At ZonMw, we recognize that achieving accessible healthcare for all requires giving those directly affected a pivotal role. While citizen science may seem like a new field, in practice, it bears striking similarities to participation. We have extensive experience with various participatory approaches and continue to explore new methods that empower citizens and patients, allowing for more equitable participation. The valuable insights gained from these endeavors are gladly shared with participants, aiding them in shaping their own projects and investigations. During our workshop, we will delve into the following questions: • How can citizen science be successfully integrated into your project? What lessons have we learned from past mistakes, and what successes have we encountered? • What resources and stakeholders are necessary to facilitate this process? • What personal commitment does it entail? • What challenges and ethical dilemmas might arise along the way? However, it's important to note that our perspective as a funding organization is not all-encompassing. We acknowledge that we are continuously learning and don't have all the answers (yet). Following the presentation we eagerly invite participants to engage in discussion and collaborate in seeking answers. Our aim is to approach these matters through multiple lenses, including: • The expertise of individuals with lived experiences or patients, • The perspectives of scientists or project leaders, • The insights of healthcare professionals or caregivers, and • The perspectives of close associates, caregivers, and the community surrounding the target group of your project or research. True innovation doesn't stem from a singular perspective behind a desk; rather, it thrives through collective learning and reflection. Together, our objective is to deepen our understanding and collectively advance the knowledge shared within the workshop. Let us reignite our inspiration, gather new insights, and foster the development of fresh knowledge collaboratively. Intended methods After a plenary presentation of half an hour (max), we will divide the participants into small groups. In these groups, they will rotate between different stakeholders' perspectives, building upon the input provided by previous groups. Towards the end, we will allocate 10 minutes for reflection, allowing individuals to process their learning experiences and share them. We kindly request that the organization of the conference provides us with names and affiliations of participants in advance, enabling us to organize the groups accordingly. Maximum number of participants: according to the format, it is set at 20, but we believe that a maximum of 40 participants would also work out well.

27 - Citizen science empowered public spaces: chances and challenges for designing AI-based Artworks to enhance human encounters and social health in public space

Masi Mohammadi, Leonie van Buuren, Barbara Groot, Tamar Shahinian, Somaya Ben Allouch, Saskia Robben, Marwan El Morabet, Marja Peltenburg, Marlene Hoyneck, Ivor Swaab

Room Inspire (DL)

Neighbourhoods affect our health in various ways. In parallel, our modern society faces multiple health challenges, including an increased number of older people (with dementia), the social gap and health differences based on socioeconomic status, ethnicity, and age, and different mental health stressors such as social isolation. These challenges, in turn, call for solutions to improve self and collaborative management in our neighbourhoods. Responding to the above developments, this workshop examines the phenomenon of creative placemaking that involves integrating AI-based artworks into the design of public spaces to improve health and well-being. A growing number of studies reveals how the design of public spaces can preserve and promote our social connections and, thereby, (perceived) quality of life. Having some form of community and social interaction in the neighbourhood is a precondition for creating informal networks. Especially for people in vulnerable situations, outdoor space design is decisive when it comes to establishing social cohesion. The workshop focuses explicitly on public familiarity, which refers to short, repeated encounters between neighbours and contributes to feelings of safety and social acceptance. These encounters can be supported by AI technology. By creating meaningful experiences that cater to the interests and (cognitive) capabilities of older people (with dementia), creative placemaking aims to influence social health and promote engagement and agency in individuals (with dementia) living in neighbourhoods. Citizens-led design of public spaces is becoming increasingly prominent in This approach promises to unleash the power of collective effort, raise awareness and community involvement to advance scientific research, promote public engagement, and generate data for scientific analysis. It also advocates for the agency and rights of individuals (with dementia) as users of these spaces. Infusing citizen science with creative place-making appears to be a highly complex yet illuminating matter. Therefore, this workshop explores the chances and challenges of smart solutions to turn public spaces into a vibrant and inclusive environment that brings people (with dementia and other neighbourhood inhabitants) together, stimulates creativity, and contributes to overall public familiarity. The workshop examines factors that influence the design of AI-based living environments where citizen-led

solutions and ethical values are integrated. During our presentations and interaction with the workshop participants, we will experience the (ethical, methodological and practical) matters relating to the citizen science design approach, the methodology and the process of participatory research, design and development process of an AI-based Artwork applied in our real-life projects, as well as the changing nature of human encounters in public spaces, and how an art-work can be utilised to encourage social interactions and encounters in public spaces. The workshop will lead to insights into the dynamics between AI- artwork, place-making, and social health through the lens of a citizen science approach.

28 - Tools to meaningfully involve citizen scientists and professionals

Annemarie Wagemakers, Maud ter Bogt, Mellany van Bommel, Samantha Elkhuisen, Kris Bevelander
Room Inform (DL)

Background. Many (research) projects aim to include citizen scientists for reasons such as taking citizen's perspectives into account, developing tailored projects, having more data collected, showing the contribution of citizen science and/or increasing citizens' knowledge and empowerment. For professional scientists, it is a challenge to engage citizens in research activities. Usually, citizens do not come by themselves, but need to be invited, especially in case where citizens are vulnerable. Participation levels are often lower (i.e. informing and consulting), while higher participation levels are desired (i.e. co-creation). Professionals need also be aware of their own role and reflect on this, especially when learning and empowerment are goals, as these processes are mutual. Furthermore, there are several issues that come with citizen science, for example: are the right citizens represented, is the capacity of citizens and professionals sufficient, is the topic feasible for citizen science and how are expectations managed. To deal with these issues, tools can be used to stimulate interaction, to guide these processes, and to simultaneously provide (actionable) knowledge.

Aim and benefit of the workshop. In this workshop, participants will learn how to meaningfully involve citizens and professionals in (research) projects. Mutual learning is the core and the topics addressed in the workshop will be based on the issues identified by participants. The benefit for participants is that they learn about the topics they are interested in and that they simultaneously learn about different citizen science tools and how to use the tools in a meaningful way.

Program of the workshop. The workshop starts by making a dynamic learning agenda about what participants want to gain from this workshop for their own context. A dynamic learning agenda may be used in sessions where professionals and citizens cooperate, as it provides valuable insights into all participants' needs. Next, we will integrate these learning points into different tools to facilitate a mutual learning process. Tools that will be used are 'a rich picture' and 'cross the line'. A rich picture is a way to explore, acknowledge and define a situation and express it through diagrams to create a preliminary mental model. A rich picture can help to open discussion and come to a broad, shared understanding of a situation. Based on this understanding, participants are invited to formulate a couple of thought-provoking statements to further explore and discuss about with the cross the line tool. Cross the line is an inspiring tool that takes statements as basis for people to choose sides. It stimulates people to move and think, and people's perspectives literally become visible. This position forms the starting point of further discussion. At the end of the workshop, participants will reflect on the initial learning agenda to see what insights are gained. Finally, participants are invited to formulate personal actions for everyone's own context.

52 - Á la recherche du santé perdue: exploring tech-based solutions through co-creation to support quality of life in transitions following the diagnosis of an invisible disability

Francesca Toso, Esther Bloem

Room Invite (DL)

Illnesses and disabilities can be identified as strong transition moment in someone's life. They imply transitioning from the belief of being a healthy and autonomous person to a disabled person, with the negative implications that societies still project on diverse conditions. The impact on the body itself, on the care rituals that enter in place, and on the general perceived psychological well-being reflects on the perceived quality of life of each person, questioning personal values, and requiring behavioural changes to different extent. When people are diagnosed with a disability they encounter social stigma, and when the disability is invisible - that is not visible from the outside yet impacting on everyday activities - they can also experience imposter syndrome, not being taken seriously or unbelieved from their social and professional network and even from unemphatic physicians. People diagnosed with invisible disabilities often turn to patient associations to seek support in the transition through community-based sense making (Cerón-Guzmán et al., 2022; O'Kane et al., 2016). When they are diagnosed with chronic illnesses they find or develop their own tools to accept the transition and cope with the new identity, from self-management support tools to self-tracking personal informatics solutions. Technologies has become a mean to find support and re-balance the lifestyle according to personal values beyond the disability itself: they adapt to each person's needs based on their individual values and needs. In this workshop, co-organized with the Schildklier Organizatie Nederland (SON), the participants will explore what does it mean for different people to live with thyroid diseases and in which way it affects their quality of life. How did the diagnosis impact on their lives? How did their life values change over time? How did they adapt their life with chronic illnesses to it? How do technologies support them in coping with residual symptoms, reaching to professionals and find community support? How can technologies be improved

to better respond to the needs and wishes of people with thyroid diseases? As much as the adoption of a specific technology can change our behaviour, adopting a technology that supports life with a disability is not always a choice (Forlano, 2023). With co-design practices and a citizen science approach, people with disabilities become co-creators through focus-groups, bringing their own life experience via interviews and other qualitative research methods (Smeenk et al., 2018), co-designing with professionals (Babbage et al., 2022; Donetto et al., 2015; Kulnik et al., 2019; Nasr et al., 2016; Ramos et al., 2020) and evaluating designs in Living Labs settings before they get on the market (Toso et al., 2023). Recently, persons with disabilities are getting more and more involved in the development of assistive technologies through co-creation practices, as they are considered experts of what life with a disability implies. There is still work to do to make sure that the technical solutions take into account the medical needs as much as the personal wishes in a non-stigmatizing way (Isselsteijn et al., 2020).

Monday, October 30 (17:00-18:00)

Poster session I; 60 minutes (29-47)

Room Atrium (TMC)

29 - IdeenLauf - Social impulses for science and research policy

Emma Waltersbacher

What will the future of digital nursing be like? What effects do microplastics have on the human hormone system? Which biomarkers are useful for diagnosing chronic post-viral diseases such as long Covid and ME/CFS?

These and many other questions were raised in the participatory initiative 'IdeenLauf'. IdeenLauf was a project initiated by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research in which the population in Germany was invited to pose their questions for science. More than 14,000 questions were collected between January and April 2022 and then grouped into thematic clusters by a citizen panel and two science panels. The 59 clusters that were created in the process are documented in a report and provide new ideas and impulses for research and research policy in Germany.

Many of the questions submitted were related to health issues. From questions on gender-specific differences in medical research to genetic engineering and post-viral diseases: People show great interest in health-related topics and issues. The poster illustrates the process of co-creative knowledge production in the IdeenLauf - project. The health-related questions can be presented using additional lists.

30 - Engaging Young People as Co-researchers in Mental Health research during the COVID-19 crisis: Ethical and Practical reflections

Signe H. Poulsen, Nina Maindal, Anne Harrits, Gitte Kragh

Engaging young people as co-researchers in mental health research holds great promise for both youth and research outcomes. However, there is a limited amount of literature and evidence on the value creation, impact, and challenges associated with this approach. During the COVID-19 pandemic, we initiated a collaboration with five young non-scientists (aged 18-20) as co-researchers. Our objectives were to gain a comprehensive understanding of young people's mental health and co-create targeted communication materials, and secondly, to explore the benefits of a co-researcher collaboration for both young individuals and the research project. We examined the involvement of co-researchers in planning, data collection, analysis, and presentation of results. The evaluation of the co-researcher collaboration involved interviews with the coresearchers, an evaluation workshop, and a questionnaire completed by the researchers. The results showed that the collaboration brought valuable insights and perspectives, and involving coresearchers proved effective in engaging young people. However, the collaboration also showed a need for careful implementation, clear communication, mutual understanding, and recognizing coresearchers' competencies are crucial. Our experience showed that young non-scientific coresearchers can significantly contribute to mental health research by providing unique perspectives and empowering young people.

31 - Participating in Place-Based Citizen Science: The Impact on Subjective Well-being of Refugee Youth

Ekaterina Egorova, Javier Martinez

Citizen Science and health is a rapidly emerging strand within the citizen science field. The mainstream of this work appears to be represented by projects that are directly related to personal health, whereby scientists and patients are jointly working on the better management of health conditions. Our poster presents a different angle – the impact of placebased citizen science (which is not focussing on health) on subjective well-being (SWB) more broadly. We first argue for SWB that

follows a bottom-up approach, relying on people's own assessments of their satisfaction with multiple domains of life. Second, we present a citizen science project where temporarily displaced youth explore public spaces of their new home towns and collect various types of data related to the environment. Finally, we report on our mixed-method impact assessment study that reveals how participation in citizen science positively affects the SWB of refugee youth. We suggest that place-based citizen science demonstrates the potential for transformative impact and increased resilience of communities and ecosystems alike. Especially in the context of residential displacement, which puts individuals into an emotionally-depleting and stressful state for an extended period of time, place-based citizen science can become a form of curated sociability or naturebased social prescription. We conclude by calling for the active inclusion of refugees and temporarily-displaced families in citizen science, contributing to their restoration and wellbeing.

32 - Engaging Older Adults in Large-Scale Co-Design Activities for late-life loneliness: A Citizen Science Approach

Sefora Tunc, Femke Nijboer, Angelica M Tinga, Monique Tabak

This research presents a novel approach to engage older adults in large-scale co-design activities by combining citizen science and co-design fiction methodologies. To address the societal challenge of late-life loneliness, we solicited narratives from older adults via a local newspaper, offering a platform for active participation and contribution. This call-to-action yielded 71 responses, from which 19 distinct user needs were identified. We argue that this approach allows older adults to contribute on their own terms as they decide where and how to contribute, thus democratizing the design process and fostering inclusivity. The results also highlight the importance of using familiar channels of communication, simple research methodologies, and local heroes to motivate participation, as well as the need for transparency about the outcomes. The findings provide valuable insights for researchers and designers who involve older adults in co-design activities, and showcase the potential of citizen science as a tool for large-scale, inclusive, and democratic design research.

33 - Involving patients via the "Austrian Patient Council"

Anna Teufel, Elisabeth Klager, Hannah Hausegger, Maria Kletečka-Pulker, Eva Schaden

Patients and loved ones are experts by experience and complete the picture next to healthcare professionals. To increase the involvement of patients in health research we have established the Austrian Patient Council (APC) and accompanied the process scientifically to demonstrate our learnings in its first year of existence.

In April 2022 we issued a call for applications. Members were selected based on predefined criteria (patient experience, participation motivation, age, gender). We did one online survey at the beginning (expectations about the work as APC members) and one at the end of the APC's first year (experiences and satisfaction). Furthermore, we heard intermediate feedback and did 5 individual interviews with members to collect more structured feedback.

We received 44 applications and invited 18 members fitting the predefined criteria. We selected 10 men and 8 women, aged 27 to 78 (mean 50.4 years) from 5 federal provinces with a variety of lived patient experiences. Although, we headed for a mixed group, only formally highly educated persons that are moreover very eager to be empowered applied. After the kick-off in May 2022, we gathered quarterly and did three educational workshops.

Thanks to the LBG OIS Center funding, we could remunerate the council members' work. The evaluation shows that the success of the first cycle was facilitated by discussing interesting topics, good time management, joint activities and very little administrative effort for the members. After the completion of the first year in April 2023, 13 council members showed an active interest in further activity.

34 - What are the barriers and supports to a return to health for those living with long COVID? - a patient-led, peer-to-peer qualitative project

Ingrid Nielsen, Sarah Olson, Rodol Paguirigan, Shiraz Bhoja, Margaret Yu, Susie Goulding, Elaine McEntee, Marcia Bruce, Paul Fairie, Maria Santana

Long COVID is now recognized as a debilitating illness that affect individuals in unique and multifarious ways. While much focus is on understanding etiology, social and economic determinants of health are an essential component to managing and recovering from disease, especially in contexts of global pandemics. Using the Patient and Community Engagement (PaCER) approach, this patient led team conducted a qualitative peer-to-peer research project looking to understand what matters most to patients when it comes to a return to health from long COVID. Through an iterative process the team of 6 students developed their research question and co-designed a qualitative study to include the lived-experience expertise and perspective at all phases of project activities. Thematic and narrative analysis were approaches to analyze data collected through focus groups and individual interviews. Collectively the team identified six themes that were central to returning to health and shared four recommendations to support more patient centric policy and practice for moving forward. This project shares suggestions to approaches and best practices to working with this unique population in similar

qualitative projects moving forward, as well the findings provide key insights to more effective and relevant health care policy and practice to improve outcomes for this growing patient population.

35 - IBD Partnerships: A Patient-Led Peer to Peer project using arts based approaches to improve shared decision making

Sandra Zelinsky

Co-producing research with Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD) patients to understand their values, needs and priorities when making treatment decisions will potentially improve shared decision-making between IBD patients and their healthcare providers (HCPs). To facilitate this process patients and HCPs must have a common understanding of expected medication benefits, risks and the potential impact on quality of life. The information available to facilitate this conversation must be aligned and reflect the priorities that IBD Patients and Healthcare Providers consider when making treatment decisions. Both parties can then share information and work towards an agreement to what treatment plan should be implemented.

This poster presentation will highlight 4 phases of a patient-led peer to peer, with support from clinician-researchers, project. In phase 1, patient focus groups were held to understand what matters most to IBD patients when making treatment decision which informed the codevelopment of a National patient survey and a mirror image copy of a healthcare provider (HCP) survey; in Phase 2, we held National insight meetings with IBD Healthcare Providers (HCP) and Patients to elicit feedback and insights from the survey results and discuss next steps; in Phase 3, a Digital Storytelling Workshop was held where IBD Patients created personal and impactful digital stories on what matters most to them when making treatment decisions to improve shared decision making; in Phase 4 (still in progress) is the co-development of HCP Reflective Educational Workshops to improve Shared Decision Making using Patient Digital Stories for educational purposes.

36 - Towards the baseline of health research infrastructure: the development of the Self Research Network Netherlands (Z.O.N.N.)

Gaston Remmers

In the Netherlands, the health care system is thought to operate at different levels or lines of care. The first line of care is the general physician, the second one links to local and regional hospitals and paramedic services, the third one is embodied by the specialized academic hospitals and carecenters. Yet, increasingly, the 'zero' line of care is recognized, which is the citizen that takes care of his/her own health. Especially in the wake of healthy lifestyle management, the 'zero-line of care' is becoming more and more important. In analogy of this, in this poster we will present the 'zero line of health research'. We will argue that the observational and experimental capacities of citizens constitute the base line of health research. Their research efforts lead to functional solutions for the involved citizens and to hypothesis that entail health value for others but need further exploration. Internationally, these are known under labels such as Do-it-Yourself medicine (Wexler, 2022) or Personal Science (Wolf and Groot, 2020). Yet, the zero line of health research is organized in a very fragmented way. There is hardly general accessible infrastructure available regarding methodology, ethics, funding, publications or data infrastructure (Transitieteam GROZ, 2019). At the same time, this type of research tends to have little profile among either research or health professionals. Lots of potentially rich citizen science in the health domain hence remains unused. The poster will outline the organization of the Dutch Zelf Onderzoek Netwerk Nederland (Z.O.N.N.; literally Self Research Network Netherlands). ZONN aligns communities linked to a diversity of health conditions such as heart failure, cancer, epilepsy, diabetes, rare diseases etc. Together they constitute at least 10.000 people engaged in some sort of bottom-up citizen science. Z.O.N.N. develops an online course for self research and 'workplaces' for self research, while building networks with established health research institutions.

37 - Beta Catchers: Crowd-Powered Analysis of Neuropathology for Alzheimer's Disease Research

Lisa Gusman, Pietro Michelucci, Brittany N. Dugger, Michael J. Keiser, Paz Santander, Margaret Lane, Lise Minaud, Gretė Vaičaitytė, Ravish Dussaruth, Shino Magaki, Jerry Lou

The Human Computation Institute (HCI) piloted a citizen science project leveraging new human computation methods to engage public volunteers in the crowd-based analysis of whole slide images (WSI) of the human brain. This project addresses the need to scale high quality neuropathological evaluations and increase outreach and education regarding Alzheimer's (AD) among communities disproportionately affected by the disease such as Hispanics. We implemented a stepwise series of online tasks that were completed by public volunteers. Some of these steps incorporated "wisdom of crowd" algorithms to combine multiple non-expert answers into a single expert-like answer. We compared these "crowd answers" to gold standard data generated by neuropathologists for two major pathology categories: cored plaques and cerebral amyloid angiopathies. Our methods successfully aggregated non-expert answers to consistently achieve a level of agreement with gold standard data equivalent to expert interrater agreement. These approaches support the rapid

production of high-volume datasets for use in machine learning development to provide deeper phenotyping of neurodegenerative diseases. An online platform, called Beta Catchers, will be used to execute the first ever de-novo analysis of Alzheimer's histopathology imagery by a crowd of volunteers, providing a culturally responsive outreach and inclusion program for impacted Hispanic communities to represent themselves in discussions with researchers.

38 - Defining research priorities in the stoma care

Villa G., Spina P.R., Balestra G.L., Sapucci G., Di Leo S., Caione N., Maculotti D., Manara D.F., Ghirotto L.

Background Approximately 2,000,000 individuals worldwide live with an ostomy, with 650,000 residing in Europe. Extensive studies consistently show that having an ostomy significantly negatively impacts the quality of life for individuals and their partners. Identifying factors contributing to a diminished quality of life and finding effective solutions is crucial. Additionally, prioritising research on the most concerning ostomy-related problems is essential.

Aim As part of a larger stoma care program, researchers from various backgrounds and non-researchers, including the Italian patient association, family members of ostomy patients, healthcare professionals, and stoma care specialists, aim to design research to define priorities in stoma care. The team plans to develop a survey involving ostomy patients and healthcare professionals through a participatory approach to identify research priorities.

Results The team will conduct a literature review on ostomy implications and problems alongside a qualitative study exploring the experiences of patients and family members. Based on the findings, the team will define priority research areas and administer a survey to individuals with an ostomy, assessing their agreement and prioritisation of these areas also considering age, social and work context. The survey will also allow participants to suggest additional areas of investigation. After piloting, the final survey will be distributed through various channels.

Discussion The survey findings will inform large-scale studies on research priorities for ostomy patients. They will guide future grant applications, investigators, and funders. Ultimately, the goal is to improve the condition of individuals with an ostomy by implementing evidence-based practices aligned with research priorities set by patients and their families.

39 - Research agenda's truly reflecting patients' needs: the case of the Dutch Brain Foundation

Carina Pittens, Vicky van de Berg, Kimberley Catsman, Jurriaan Oosterman, Els van der Rhee

Many (Dutch) health research-funders (HRF) have nowadays research agenda's reflecting patient's input. Since many HRFs are funded by and for people with certain health conditions ('collectebusfondsen'), they see it as their societal duty to spend resources on what their supporters consider important. Moreover, HRFs are considered an important player in realizing a more needs-oriented health research system, since they have the power to steer research into a certain direction. However, establishing impacting research agenda's that truly reflect patients' needs and which result in concrete research projects and related activities is far from self-evident.

With this poster presentation, we want to showcase the process and outcomes of the agenda-setting process of the Dutch Brain Foundation (DBF). To do justice to patient's needs, the agenda was not restricted to certain domains. Based on the principles of the Dialogue Model, people with brain disorders and (in)formal caregivers were asked about the experienced impacts in daily life due to the brain disorder, which resulted in a wide range of impacts covering all life domains. In a follow-up step (currently ongoing), a wide range of experts (from (social) researchers, tech-innovators to health-insurers and policy-makers) will be asked to formulate opportunities to address this wide range of impacts. This will result in a concrete overview that the DBF can use to better align their follow-up actions with patients' needs.

40 - Citizen Science for Understanding the Health and Well-being of Fishers: Empirical Insights for Sustainable Coastal Communities

Isa Elegbede

This research study aims to explore the role of citizen science in understanding the health of fishers and its implications for sustainable coastal communities. By actively involving fishers as researchers and data collectors, this study employs a mixed-methods approach, including surveys, interviews, and observations, to gather comprehensive and empirical data on the physical health, mental well-being, occupational hazards, and lifestyle factors among fishers. The findings of this research will contribute to evidence-based interventions, policy recommendations, and community-driven initiatives aimed at enhancing the health and well-being of fishers while promoting the long-term sustainability of coastal communities. Through collaborative partnerships between fishers, researchers, and policymakers, this research bridges the gap between scientific knowledge and local wisdom, empowering fishers to become active participants in shaping their own health outcomes. This study underscores the importance of ongoing monitoring, engagement, and the integration of fishers' perspectives in achieving resilient and thriving coastal communities with improved health outcomes for fishers.

41 - Engaging citizens in environmental health monitoring

Ioannis Tavantzis, Aikaterini Bakousi, Aikaterini Stamou, Eleni Evangelidou, Nikolaos Nagkoulis, Konstantinos Grizos, Theocharis Vlachopanagiotis, Efstratios Stylianidis

Citizen science has emerged as a powerful tool for advancing our understanding of environmental and health-related issues. In our study we focused on citizen science in environmental health, specifically in the context of measuring and interpreting three key environmental indexes that impact health: air pollution, UV exposure, and NDVI. These are indicators of environmental health and have been linked to a range of physical and mental health outcomes. Our study aims to investigate the effectiveness of presenting these indexes to citizens in both conventional and vulgarized units, with the goal of enhancing their understanding of the potential health impacts of the urban environment. Through the participation of citizens in the collection and interpretation of data, we hope to promote greater citizen engagement both in the public dissemination of relevant data as well as citizen science and environmental monitoring while contributing to the broader goal of improving public health.

42 - Xaire: how a large-scale air quality citizen science campaign can improve health quality assessments and promote community knowledge and collective action

Josep Perelló, Isabelle Bonhoure

This poster presents a large-scale air quality collective measurement (xAire), that followed a citizen science methodology. A broad partnership with 1,650 people from communities around 18 primary schools across Barcelona provided the capacity to obtain unprecedented high-resolution NO₂ (nitrogen dioxide) levels. The communities first collectively identified the relevant spots to be measured in their neighborhoods. In a well-coordinated effort, they placed at the same time 800 diffusion tubes in the proximity of 18 primary schools. The tubes were collected exactly 4 weeks after.

This way, new and precise information on the air quality in the vicinity of the schools was obtained. These data and their interpretation were presented by the kids to the City Council authorities. The results encourage strengthening collaboration with local communities when exploring environmental health issues.

These new data also made possible an updated asthma Health Impact Assessment. It is shown that NO₂ levels vary considerably with at some cases very high levels. More than a 1,000 new cases of childhood asthma could be prevented each year by lowering NO₂ levels. Also, predictive NO₂ models in the city have incorporated this citizen science data as a reliable data source. The data have had the models capacity to improve the spatial high resolution. After the project, families and schools have been able to better assess and to take individual and collective actions to mitigate NO₂ concentration levels around the schools and in each neighborhood. Finally, the results were published in the form of scientific paper, the data were published as Open Data and the protocol reported in a specialized scientific journal (MethodsX), in order to maximize the reproducibility of the study.

43 - Health promotion and homelessness in Germany. Co-defining challenges, co-designing methods, co-creating solutions

Carmen Anthonj

For people experiencing homelessness, shelters and public restrooms are often the only option to access drinking water, sanitation and hygiene (WASH) services to promote their health. Despite the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 6 call to “ensure water and sanitation for all” in order to promote health and reduce exposure to infectious disease, and despite the Human Right to Water and Sanitation, the needs of homeless people are not met; WASH inequalities and the resulting burden of disease remain hidden and under-researched in official statistics.

This ongoing exploratory project in Bonn, Germany, in collaboration with the City of Bonn, Caritas and Verein für Gefährdetenhilfe aims to i) understand the challenges that people experiencing homelessness in urban areas face with regard to WASH insecurity, by ii) involving people experiencing homelessness as key stakeholders to co-design methods and techniques most suitable to capture the challenges they are facing, and ultimately iii) jointly identify suitable interventions through participatory inclusive mapping.

Different activities are being undertaken and include in-depth walking interviews with people experiencing homelessness; joint inspections and spot checks of WASH infrastructure (in)accessible to people experiencing homelessness; mental mapping and participatory mapping; focus group discussions with different relevant stakeholders such as representatives of homeless associations, authorities and social workers supporting and working with people experiencing homelessness. Preliminary findings, the research approach to a high risk, high gain project, challenges faced, and their implications on the progress of the project will be introduced.

44 - SDG OLYMPIAD - A global competition to select and support youth teams in developing and deploying citizen science solutions for human and planetary health.

Rosy Mondardini, Francois Grey

- The SDG Olympiad is a four-step competition for youth based on concrete challenges set by experts from UN agencies and researchers from top academic institutions. It's about youth teams developing solutions for local needs.
- At the core of the SDG Olympiad is a simple but bold idea: young people have the ability to use citizen science tools and methodologies for tackling the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in their communities. It's about scaling up youth action to reach millions.
- The theme of the SDG Olympiad is open source health solutions, stretching from human health challenges like infectious diseases to planetary health challenges like climate resilience. It's about youth helping communities help themselves.
- At successive steps of the competition, youth teams pitch their solutions, develop robust prototypes, deploy the results and find ways to sustain their impact, all the while growing their entrepreneurial confidence and their personal well-being. It's about young people learning how to take great ideas all the way to the finish line.

The SDG Olympiad is being developed by the SDG Solution Space in Geneva, the Learning Planet Institute in Paris, with the support of Citizen Science Zurich. Over the last five years, these vanguard labs have hosted SDG Summer Schools in collaboration with UNESCO, WHO, ITU and the Global Fund, amongst others, with support from the EU, national governments, philanthropies and corporations.

45 - Highlights of the need for a Science of Engagement (SoE) in health research and innovation for Citizen Science

Nancy Marlett

This poster summarizes the history, current best practice and possible futures of citizen science for health that are needed to democratize future health care, planning and research. The SoE manuscript (Marlett, 2022) considers the history, science and philosophy, methods and theory needed to train citizen scientist patients and members of underrepresented communities to conduct peer research. Health related CS can foster new opportunities to explore new roles for patients and new methods and theory that are participatory, adaptable, robust. The methods are designed to identify main concerns of populations, share real life experiences, co-produce pragmatic solutions.

The history includes major shifts in health research from behaviour management, educational programs and peer support to peer research that can make a difference. Best practices of CS models of engagement from collecting or providing data, advising, collaborating and citizen led research.

Futures of CS in health care capture both JEDI principles to challenge systemic discrimination and the inclusion of patients as key stakeholders in co design and production of technologies. As the shift to prevention as part of merging physical, digital and biological technologies accelerates, citizens will assume more control of monitoring their health and health technologies. The poster ends with a snapshot of the philosophy of a new SoE that will enhance the scope of CS for health to ensure that the possibilities of JEDI and technology are met because patients and citizens are key stakeholders in their health, health care and future.

46 - Citizen Science 4 Health: SDU Moves

Linnea Marie Sjöberg, Jens Troelsen, Anne Kathrine Overgaard, Thomas Kaarsted

'SDU Moves' is a strategy at University of Southern Denmark's (SDU) according to the UN Sustainability Development Goals. SDU Moves focus on SDG 3, Health and Well-being, by aiming to empower staff to enhance movement during their workday through a Citizen Science co-creation method.

Through repetitive activities, events, and workshops SDU Moves inspires and motivates employees – our citizens – to a behavioral change. By now SDU moves has documented an impressive participation in planned movements activities as well as activities on their own eg walking meetings which reflects a change in working culture toward a focus on a more active lifestyle at work. We conducted a baseline survey for all employees at SDU in November 2020 where the citizens could elaborate on expectations and wishes to the strategy. The citizens thoughts and ideas were followed up in the annual survey until november 2023.

Based on survey responses the strategy key initiatives were initiated, for example walking meetings. To ensure SDU Moves were implemented throughout the university, a key element was also to engage movement ambassadors, hold workshops, and send newsletters to get as many employees involved in realizing the strategy. This poster presents the key results from the three survey rounds. Especially results from the baseline since we are working on how to inspire more workplaces to integrate movement during a sedentary workday. This will lead to peer-review scientific paper later this year.

47 - Enhancing Informed Consent in Citizen Science for Healthcare: Incorporating Quality Labels into Consent Forms

Yentl van Dop, Ilona Wilmont

This research paper explores the incorporation of quality labels into consent forms to enhance informed consent in citizen science for healthcare. A literature review and analysis of privacy themes in consent forms were conducted using Atlas.ti as a basis for the labels. Three labels are proposed: a nutrition score-based label, a concise summary label, and a grading scheme for privacy assessment. The findings suggest that quality labels can improve transparency, clarity, and privacy protection. These labels provide standardized ways to engage participants in consent forms, enabling participants to make informed decisions. Implementation of quality labels in citizen science can promote a more ethical and trustworthy environment for healthcare-related research. Further research is needed to validate the effectiveness and acceptance of these labels. The study contributes to improving informed consent practices in citizen science for healthcare.

Tuesday, October 31 (09:00-10:30)

Workshops III; 90 minutes (session 48-53)

48 - Science Citizenship: The Case of Citizen Science NOW

Jeroen Vonk, Chloë Gerritsen, Robert Marinescu-Muster, Sjoerd de Vries

Room TL1336 (TMC)

Even though there are many citizen science initiatives, the competencies, knowledge and skills needs of citizens, involved scientists, citizen science facilitators, and others among them have often been left unnoticed. When citizens are involved, they usually get roles assigned to them. The question is: how to get citizens pro-active in involving the universities in their own challenges? What competences do they need in order to do this? Activating the citizen scientist! Bringing these competences into the picture has been the goal of Citizen Science NOW. We offer a workshop in which we will explore these questions. Based on the identified competence needs in citizen science, which empowers citizens to not only be active participants, but also lead in their own challenges. Moreover, what would 'science citizenship' mean for researchers? The main questions are: 1. How to find the balance as researchers in working together pro-active citizen scientists and citizen activists? 2. Which competences do citizen scientists need to not just participate, but lead responsibly in citizen science? Our presentation Our intention is to present Citizen Science NOW and its results. We will present the Future Design methodology, the main competencies that are critical for citizen scientists, and the learning resources created to activate citizen science. It empowers citizens to participate and lead in their challenges. Intended methods We intend to organize a presentation of the project, followed by two discussion moments, each containing a task. In the first task, we will ask the participants to form groups of four persons and explore the balance between active citizen scientists and citizen activists. In the second task, the participants explore the citizen competences to become active and leading. In between, the results of the first group discussion will be shared with everyone. This will also happen after the second group discussion. What will the participants achieve? The participants get to explore the competencies that are important for active citizen scientists. As many of the researchers that will participate are into citizen science projects themselves, it will create awareness. They will deepen their understanding of the way in which they can balance working with active citizen scientists and citizen activists. It is specifically relevant for researchers involved in citizen science in the health domain, since many citizens have a vast interest in dealing with health care (problems). The Citizen Science for Health conference would be a great opportunity, both for us and for the participants, to think about what it means to have active citizenship. To think about the future development of citizen science and the implications that democratization brings with it.

49 - Citizen Science Incubator - Getting your project off the ground

Pietro Michelucci, Jennifer Couch, Muki Hacklay, Attila Szantner

Room TL2148 (TMC)

Does your citizen science project have the key ingredients needed for success? How can you create a compelling proposal? Overview Obtaining financial support can be a daunting, overwhelming, and seemingly endless task. By gathering investigators with successful funding track records and extensive grant writing experience, this workshop offers conference participants the opportunity to learn how to craft a strong proposal. Those who have successfully received funding will share their strategies and you will hear stories of how project leaders pieced together funding from various sources. The workshop may also provide an opportunity to find complementary partners for new projects. Objectives • Learn what it takes to put together a strong proposal • Learn how successfully funded investigators got funding for their work • Participants will develop new projects or ideas into pitches • Participants will receive feedback on their pitches Format This 90-minute workshop will be split into three parts: • Panel - success stories and lessons learned (40 minutes) A panel of investigators who have successfully pieced together funding will describe strategies and lessons learned and answer related questions.

50 - Building participative environments

Mieke Cardol, Christine Dedding, Zsuzsu Tavy, Meralda Slager

Room Inform (DL)

In Citizen Science for health the role of participants is of vital importance. In many participation projects, research or quality of care projects, the role of participants is weak or weaker than the position of scientists or project leaders. Most likely the participants are involved in a later stage. This has several severe consequences. It means that the goals and conditions are already defined and it is hard for participants to restart the discussion. Another effect of late participation is that a lot of *work* that comes with participation has to be done by participants. They have to be trained, they have to find ways to be

closely involved with their peers in order to rule out the n=1 and they are not allowed to speak about their messy experience stories.

For participation to be successful and meaningful and by that is meant that participants can share their experience, give their practical knowledge and use their own messy stories, it is important that participative environments are created. This means that goals and outcomes are not set at forehand but are part of the participation process. It is also important that there is an open and friendly climate that stimulates the dialogue that is so important to obtain mutual insight and make changes.

In 2013 Dedding and Slager wrote in 'De rafels van participatie'. For this book various expertise was given around cases that were presented to the authors by participants who were involved in research projects or projects to improve quality of care. The cases showed various dilemma's or practical issues that the participants were confronted with. It also showed that still a lot of work has to be done to ensure participative environments. In this book the authors Dedding & Slager presented the following definition of participation:

A situational and interactive process in which all stakeholders in research and/or policy are in dialogue, doing justice to the lived experiences, knowledge and competences of all actors, especially individuals whose daily life and body are at stake, in all phases of the process, aiming for improvements in quality of care and a more inclusive society.

In the last decade, at different universities of applied sciences and within universities much attention is given in health research or in education programs to the conditions of participative work. Still it is of vital importance to continue to educate students and professionals what participation means and how to built participative environments. The changing concept of health means that a lot is asked from citizens. It is important to start a dialogue and understand the specific contexts of people. This requires to build participative environments.

The presenters in this workshop present their alternative conceptualization of participation. They will discuss in their presentation what this requires in terms of work in order to develop genuine participation practices.

51 - Partnership readiness and holding safe spaces in health research

Sandra Zelinsky, Ingrid Nielssen, Paul Fairie, Sadia Ahmed, Maria Santana

Room Learn-X (DL)

The aim of this session is to discuss the readiness of team members (researchers, patients, families, community members and other stakeholders) to working together in health research. In Patient-Oriented Research, community-based research and other participatory health research approaches, there is an emphasis on building trusting relationships amongst the team members. But how can trust become established and what happens when trust is broken? Help us to tackle the challenge of 'partnership competencies and readiness' and ways of 'holding safe spaces' when working together in health research teams. Using examples based on real engagement and project experiences we can collectively work through more democratic approaches to priority setting, research design, co-development of data collection tools, collective data analysis and dissemination approaches. Let's reflect, share, and discuss the challenges of onboarding, training, and assessing readiness of team members to engage and work together in research and brainstorm how to handle ethical issues when personal agendas, bias, motivations, and goals do not align with the research topic.

We will present a few real engagement and project experiences for reflection and group discussion and then we will work together to ideate and discuss the challenges and solutions of each experience. We will use sticky notes to ideate and share challenges and solutions which will then be posted to flip charts, themed out, discussed and then we will individually and collectively reflect on lessons learned.

53 - Exploring the interrelation of citizen science and patient involvement

Jacqueline Maschino, Carina Pittens, Janneke Elberse, Eva Vroonland

Room TL2187 (TMC)

Citizen science is emerging in a wide range of disciplines, from the humanities to the natural and social sciences. However, health-related citizen science projects are relatively limited, as highlighted by the European Citizen Science Association. Meanwhile, patient involvement in health research is a growing, increasingly established practise. Over a two decades period, patients and patient organisations with a variety of backgrounds have been increasingly involved in health research. Both citizen science and patient involvement recognize the value and necessity of incorporating experiential knowledge of patients and citizens, to enhance scientific processes and outcomes. Despite the similarities in this underlying principle, citizen science and patient involvement seem to be approached as two different movements. In this workshop we would like to discuss how citizen science and patient involvement are interrelated. How can we position one versus the other? And how can citizen science and patient involvement reinforce each other? Participants do not get immediate answers on these questions. The goal is to mutually learn from each other's vision, and work towards a more collective understanding on the coherence of citizen science and patient involvement. Intended lay out • Welcome and energizer on the topic • Short presentation on patient involvement On e.g. definitions and the identified roles patients can take on in research. The goal is to align the basic knowledge on patient involvement, and enable meaningful discussion. • Panel discussion with

three speakers (Carina, Jacqueline, Janneke) on the basis of statements Participants and panelspeakers show whether they agree or disagree with a statement. Thereafter the panelspeakers reflect on their argumentation, and participants are invited to add their thoughts and questions. • To work! In groups of 5, participants work on several questions, such as: o In what way are citizen science and patient involvement similar, different and/or complementary? o How should the knowledge and experiences on citizen science and patient involvement be aligned? o What could the fields of patient involvement and citizen science learn from each other? o What are challenges or barriers to combining citizen science and patient participation in health research, and how can they be addressed? o How can researchers, healthcare professionals, and policymakers promote a more collaborative and inclusive approach to health research involving both citizen science and patient participation? Once more is known about the audience of the workshop we make a definite choice for questions. • Plenary wrap-up Groups share their highlights of the groupwork, and participants individually reflect on which insights from the workshop they 'bring back' to their co-workers. Potential benefits of the participants: mutual learning between both participants and speakers, and thereby deepening their individual thoughts on the coherence between patient involvement and citizen science. As participants probably have experience with either citizen science or patient involvement, they gain insights on the one they are less familiar with. The potential benefits of all participants and speakers is a collective understanding on the beforementioned question.

Tuesday, October 31 (12:15-12:35)

Solution rooms IV; 20 minutes (session 54-57)

54 - Science Citizenship - Exploring the Important Competences

Jeroen Vonk, Chloë Gerritsen, Robert Marinescu-Muster, Sjoerd de Vries

Room Inform (DL)

Even though citizen science has been taking off and many initiatives have being started, the competencies, knowledge and skills needs of citizens, involved scientists, citizen science facilitators, and others among them have often been left unnoticed. Bringing these needs into the picture has been the goal of Citizen Science NOW. In this solution room, we offer a challenge to the participants about citizen science competences and taking up leadership; science citizenship. How can the participants think with us to address active citizenship in citizen science? What do citizens need in order to be successful in tackling local challenges? How can local citizen science structures be created most effectively? We want the input of the participants in helping think with us. The solution room will take twenty minutes. We will start by explaining the 'scan card' methodology, and then divide the participants into small groups. Proceeded by a brainstorm session, in which they will create their own scan card which contains the competences that they consider the most important for 'science citizenship'. This will be done on A3 format. In the last five minutes, we will gather their scan cards and share them with everyone. We will have an indication of what the researchers consider the most important competences. Our interest is to get their feedback on 'activating' citizen science, and finding out how citizens can take up leading roles in their challenges.

55 - Co-creation with vulnerable groups – a needs-driven, inclusive focus group methodology

Andrea Kastl, Leonhard Dobusch

Room Learn-X (DL)

Background: Focus group discussions are a participative method commonly used in qualitative health research. However, there are still unanswered questions about conducting focus groups with vulnerable groups. In order to further analyse conceptual (development of user friendly stimuli) and pragmatic challenges and facilitators, focus group discussions were carried out with vulnerable groups. Methods: Twelve focus groups with different vulnerable groups such as elderly, patients of orthopaedic and neurologic rehabilitation clinics, people with disabilities, people living in nursing homes and family care givers were conducted. In order for the different groups to be able to actively participate and contribute in the focus group discussions, the stimuli were adapted to the respective abilities and life worlds of the groups. Thereby different design thinking methods (e.g. photo stories, persona method) and language adaptations were deployed. A meta-evaluation of the perspective of the researchers who facilitated the focus groups accompanied the process. Content: The process of recruitment, development of the stimuli, the preparation of the focus groups, the implementation as well as the meta-evaluation will be discussed and become transparent in the Solution Room. Afterwards, participants are invited to critically reflect on the approach. Aim of the session: Within the format "solution room" the needs-driven focus group methodology will be introduced to the audience and critically discussed. The authors look forward to contact with other researchers with similar experiences and to share insights and feedback on the challenges and facilitators of focus group discussions with vulnerable groups.

56 - How to best integrate citizen science aspects in the implementation of the newly developed app for Intelligent Physical Exercise Training (IPET)?

Tina Dalager, Linnea Marie Sjöberg

Room Inspire (DL)

We have developed the IPET app, that targets the working population. The concept designs individually tailored exercises based on self-reported information on work profile, physical capacity, musculoskeletal pain, and general health. The physical exercises are categorized within the training domains of strength, aerobic, and functional training. The exercises can be performed during working hours or leisure time. Interventions with IPET, have previously demonstrated clinically relevant health effects (increased physical capacity, reduced musculoskeletal pain, enhanced productivity etc.), when delivered in an 'analogue' form of training diaries as hands outs. The app is currently undergoing a co-creation process, where employees within different occupations identify features need to increase use and engagement. During summer 2023, the IPET app will, based on the user identification, be refined to be ready for a pilot test. This test will include approx. 150 employees from different occupations with the objective to investigate different health effects and user engagement. In 2024, a large implementation study is planned, with approx. 750 employees from one Danish University and two Danish hospitals (approx. 50 different departments) who will be invited to use the IPET app for 9 months. A solution room session will be conducted as a 'Think Aloud' workshop where participants can share solutions on how citizen science aspects can be integrated in the implementation of the IPET app with the aim to increase reach, effect, implementation, and maintenance.

57 - Expanding the role of experts-by-experience in citizen science

Samantha Elkhuisen, Annemarie Wagemakers

Room TL2148 (TMC)

Background: Experts-by-experience bridge the gap between families in vulnerable positions, professionals, and researchers. Although experts-by-experience, including those working as citizen scientists, are playing an increasing role, their role is still evolving and not well-defined. Expanding the role of experts-by-experience within science is a challenge. In many cases, participation levels are low (e.g. informing and consulting), whereas higher participation levels are desired (e.g. co-creation). Aim of the session: In this solution room, we aim to explore how to expand the role of experts-by-experience in citizen science. Together we will share our challenges, experiences, and good practices of working with experts-by-experience in citizen science. Participants will gain knowledge on how to expand the role of experts-by-experience in science. Program of the solution room: To guide the discussion, we will present statements about the role of experts-by-experience in citizen science. Participants will be asked to score each proposition individually with colored voting cards containing both text and symbols. The score is the starting point for discussion and exploration of the topic. Statements that will be discussed relate to how to engage experts-by-experience in research activities and analysis, what they can and cannot do, what being engaged in research activities means for them, for professionals, for researchers, and for the quality of the research.

Showcases III; 20 minutes (session 58-63)

58 - Citizen science with children

Nikki Jepkema

Room Invite (DL)

In this showcase we will summarize our experiences with citizen science in the context of primary education. As researchers, we are involved in the project "Tijd voor Toekomst".

This project focuses on a promising generation for all Groningen citizens. This means breaking through poverty from generation to generation. We want to tackle this by developing a day program, an enriched school day at primary schools in the province of Groningen. In this project we deal with the social challenge of (in)equality of opportunity among children in primary education and more specifically the consequences of this on health and lifestyle. The showcase will briefly highlight steps in this whole process and we hope to discuss navigating pitfalls, resistance, challenges and opportunities in specially doing citizen science with children.

Together with a local network of children, parents, teachers, management and municipality we are worked towards an enriched school day. We involved young individuals in the process at different levels of citizen science (instrumental, distributive, participative). Through citizen science, children can actually participate. They learn how science works and get to make their own decisions in the field of health promotion. Because they think along and help decide in the activities, inform parents and provide input, there is a chance of sustainable behavioral change.

59 - Student wellbeing through Citizen Science; students, research & practice together

Rhoda Schuling, Berry van Holland, Ruby Otter-Drost

Room Play (DL)

Last year, we presented a poster on the design of the student wellbeing through citizen science project at ECSA Berlin. For this conference, we would like to present on the course the project took since then, by co-creation of the students involved, and our findings.

At the moment, we have identified what counts as urgent in student wellbeing for our own students (Hanze-context), which deviates from the professional experts' point of view, and we are identifying promising interventions that could alleviate students' reduced wellbeing mentally, physically and socially.

At the time of the conference, we will be able to present how we formed the process of co-creation and what the impact of this process, as well as the interventions, was. For the audience we wish to impart what elements crucially shaped our process and outcomes, determine which impact is vital, and how to measure this impact.

60 - Personal Science Wiki

Katharina Kloppenborg, Mad Price Ball, Bastian Greshake Tzovaras

Room TL2107 (TMC)

The Personal Science Wiki is an open, peer-produced knowledge resource about personal science – the practice of using empirical methods to explore personal questions, predominantly related to health and well-being. This type of self-directed inquiry requires a range of research skills, which can impose barriers. Despite being a largely individual practice, self-researchers often have similar questions and issues, benefitting from experiences of their peers. Developed through a user-centered design approach with the community, the wiki provides an infrastructure for a continuously evolving shared knowledge base for personal science. At the conference showcase, attendees can familiarize themselves with personal science as a practice and freely explore the wiki's content, including talks, methods, and overviews of tracking topics. Furthermore, participants are encouraged to consider contributing to the wiki. The showcase will be presented using a laptop and requires a table (preferably a high/bar table) with access to a power outlet.

61 - VRbeelding: Improving citizens perceptions on dementia through a co-created Virtual Reality experience

Gabriëlle ten Velde, Franka Bakker, Rens Brankaert, Hilco Prins, Charles van der Spek, Anjo Geluk, Jan Rietsema, Rika Roffelsen, Dinant Bekkenkamp, Marike Hettinga, Wim Trooster, Simone de Bruin

Room TL2187 (TMC)

The "VRbeelding" research project challenges public perceptions of dementia via a co-created Virtual Reality (VR) training. The project engages with citizens (among which those with dementia), experts, and researchers, in participatory design, implementation, and evaluation. The showcase offers the conference audience a unique opportunity to experience being a caregiver for a person with early-stage dementia through VR. This immersive scenario allows participants to empathize with the complexities of dementia care, challenging fear-based narratives. By immersing themselves in this caregiving experience, participants will gain valuable perspectives that can positively impact their perception of and approach to dementia care. We envision this to result in a social shift and provide individuals with dementia with autonomy and improved quality of life. The set-up requires space and power outlets for seamless presentation, enabling attendees to fully engage with the transformative VR scenario.

62 - A digital platform for citizen science

Mark Boom, Silas de Graaf, Dawid Kulikowski, Jesse Snoijer, Joep Vorage

Room TL2389 (TMC)

This showcase demonstrates an online platform designed for citizen science. The platform was developed as a bachelor project at the University of Twente in collaboration with citizen science researchers. It enables citizen science researchers to independently set up and manage studies, mainly focusing on recurring questionnaires. It includes features like a dynamic informed consent wizard as well as a communication module that allows researchers to communicate with citizens. In all areas of the platform, privacy, security and anonymity of participants is guaranteed. Throughout the user interface, a large emphasis is put on delivering a user experience that is as accessible as possible. For the audience, the main benefit of attending the showcase is gaining insight into how a well-designed digital platform could contribute to the field. The showcase consists of a presentation by two presenters, who will only require a projector or large screen.

63 - Inclusive Knowledge Translation and Dissemination in Patient-Oriented Research

Sandra Zelinsky, Ingrid Nielssen, Paul Fairie, Sadia Ahmed, Maria Santana

Room TL1251 (TMC)

The Alberta SPOR SUPPORT Unit, Patient Engagement Team at the University of Calgary works with Patient, Family & Community Research Partners, Academic Researchers, and other stakeholders to support patient-oriented research throughout the research cycle, including in knowledge translation and dissemination. In this session we would like to highlight patient-oriented research knowledge translation & dissemination products and resources that have been co-developed by people with lived experience; including the Patient Engagement Podcast (PEP Talks), the Patient Engagement Journal Club, Digital Storytelling, Patient-Led co-created posters, Patient Engagement Guidance Documents as well as other resources.

Tuesday, October 31 (14:00-15:30)

Workshops IV; 90 minutes (session 64-70)

64 - Stumbling blocks & quality criteria for youth participation

Christine Dedding, Karijn Aussems, Charlotte, Noah

Room TL1336 (TMC)

Methods: We start with a short presentation in which we introduce our national learning network on youth participation in research and the guideline for genuine collaboration that we collectively have developed. Participants will be asked to highlight the criterion they like most and one/two that might need critical reflection, or more explanation/elaboration. The latter ones will be used for the second part of the workshop in which we will collectively reflect on these by the participants selected criteria.

Content: The quality guidelines that we will share have been developed by members of the Learning Network for Youth Participation in Research. The learning network is funded by ZonMw (the Netherlands Organization for Health Research and Development), and aims to strengthen the quality of youth participation. Previously, in 2013, ten guidelines for genuine participatory research with children and young people were drawn up by researchers. The new guidelines are created in close collaboration with young people, as well as a new group of researchers, and based on recent literature. As a result, the guidelines are more in line with current practice and ensure the quality of participation that we currently aim for. Next year, the Learning Network will work on the theoretical underpinning and practical implementation of these guidelines.

Benefits for the participants:

- Connecting with other professionals who are interested in quality of youth participation
- Collectively reflect on quality guidelines for youth participation in relations to own practices and possible barriers and differences
- All participants will receive a hard copy of the guidelines to bring home.

65 - Advancing on equitable and inclusive health for women and LGBTQIA+

Ana Macedo, Anne-Sophie Gresle, Irene Lapuente, Patricia Martínez Galisteo, Joana Magalhães

Room TL2148 (TMC)

Despite the progress made in recent years, women's health research and/or care is still far from being equitable and inclusive. The reasons are varied and intersectional, with evidence showing that certain social groups are discriminated against, and specific diseases remain underdiagnosed, conditioning access to health care, with consequences for morbidity and even mortality. People don't seek out or don't speak openly to health professionals for fear of being mistreated, and in turn, health professionals still lack specific knowledge and training or might experience communication difficulties. Citizen science offers an opportunity to reduce the gap between health professionals and women and LGBTQIA+ people encouraging the participation of the latter in the research process in multiple stages, whilst pushing decision-making and the implementation of strategies that promote communication, mutual trust and further empowerment. Within the IMPETUS accelerator, 4 projects are exploring this topic: 1. "MENINA", evaluating mental health and wellbeing improvement during pregnancy; 2. "Obstetric co-evolution", analyzing the relationship between obstetric practices and mothers' mental health; 3. "Endo-Health", working towards the co-creation of experience and health outcomes questionnaires to implement a new model of care for endometriosis; and 4. "Equity in health for LGBTQIA+ people", evaluating the knowledge and perception of discrimination of general practitioners about sexual and gender minority people's health. Prompted by these projects, we propose to explore common barriers and solutions to embed and mainstream gender perspective and intersectionality within health care and research from the patient perspective.

Tuesday, October 31 (14:00-15:30) - Workshops IV; 90 minutes (session 64-70)

66 - Does Citizen Science for Health need (more) engagement

John Dierx, Ander de Keijzer, Eefje Schrauwen, Meralda T. Slager

Room Inform (DL)

The Centre of Expertise Perspective in Healthcare of Avans University of Applied Sciences pursues inclusiveness and participation in health, wellbeing and care. This, by putting people centre stage as their perspectives on their own lives form the basis of their actions and hence should be at the start from which healthcare, care and wellbeing is organized.

According to our vision, we seek to contribute to and create a healthy society for and by people through an integrated and multidisciplinary approach. Hereby focusing on lifestyle, prevention and the environment, and through the use of ICT and healthcare technology. Therefore, our research and innovation is not just for people, but with people who are directly involved. We refer to this as 'Citizen Engaged Science'.

The term '*engaged*' evokes different images and meanings as an insert between 'Citizens' and 'Science' since it has the double meaning. On the one hand it refers to actively involving citizens in research and on the other to citizens who wants to be actively involved in science to address social problems and issues.

Besides the active engagement and knowledge transfer between citizens and scientists, public involvement allows researchers to collect large-scale and realtime data. For example, recent epidemics and pandemics have shown that environmental changes, globalization, social-economic conflicts are important underlying factors for infectious disease emergence and transmission. A phenomenon that not only affects and burdens all citizens' health and wellbeing in the broadest sense, but also something that can be actively mitigated by them. In this worldwide problem, there is a need for early detection strategies and therefore citizen engaged science might be the key.

In this workshop we aim to engage participants in discussing and reflecting on the (non)sense of citizens' *engaged* science and its possible positive and negative aspects. Does Citizen Science need more engagement and what does this mean for our research?

Intended methods: In this workshop 4 presentations will be given in which will be elaborated on the theme of Engaged within Citizen Science. This will be followed by a debate in which the presenters will further discuss the theme of engagement within Citizen Science for health.

Content of workshop: One presentation is about an exploration study that has been done around the theme of citizen engaged science commissioned by the Centre of Expertise Perspective in Health. The other 3 presentations are from respectively professor John Dierx Equal opportunities for healthy Choices, Professor Ander de Keijzer, Data Science and ICT and Eefje Schrauwen, associate professor Infectious Diseases.

Potential benefits: Elaborating on the theme of citizens' *engaged* science for health. How can Citizen Science be meaningful and create an opportunity for active involvement of citizens? And what does this mean for the research agenda?

67 - Personal Science and Self-Tracking: Learning From Continuous Blood Glucose Data

Gary Isaac Wolf, Martijn de Groot, Sara Riggare, Thomas Blomseth Christiansen, Jakob Eg Larsen

Room Learn-X (DL)

How can personal science based on self-tracking help us make consequential personal discoveries? This workshop will explore the methods and principles of self-research with a focus on using records from the Nutrisense continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) program and device, along with additional self-observations. Methods and Content The workshop will consist of the following key components: 1. Introduction to Personal Science and Self-Tracking: ● Short overview (10 minutes) of the concepts, benefits, and challenges of personal science, and its relationship to the larger themes of citizen science. This introduction will include an invitation to think ahead in anticipation of the final workshop segment, in which participants will develop their own self-research question relating to diet, metabolism, and blood glucose. 2. Quantified Self "Show&Tell" Talks ● A short (7-8 minute) talk by each presenter about their blood glucose self-research, answering the questions: What did I do? How did I do it? What did I learn? ● These talks will illustrate, using practical examples, the application of key self-research methods, including formulating a good self-research question, choosing what to observe, creating easily managed records, and visualizing data to support discoveries. 3. Collaborative Workshop Activities: ● Group exercises to design and plan self-research projects using personal science. 4. Potential Benefits for Participants: By actively engaging in this workshop, participants will: ● Gain an understanding of personal science and its relation to citizen science. ● Learn practical approaches for designing and conducting self-research projects. ● Find answers to questions about benefits and challenges of minimally invasive CGM devices as instruments of self-research.

68 - CoAct for Mental Health: a hands-on workshop and a conversation co-presented by Co-Researchers and academics.

Isabelle Bonhoure, Amanda Figueras, Assumpta Mateu

Room Invite (DL)

WHO recently stated in the World mental health report “Transforming mental health for all” (2022) that “Valuing the insight of people with lived experience of mental health conditions, and giving them voice, choice and influence in multiple aspects of the mental health care system, is a vital step towards transforming mental health worldwide.” This is precisely what the CoAct for Mental Health project has put into practice, in the frame of the 3-years CoAct project, financed by the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No. 873048 and done in collaboration with the Catalan Federation of Mental Health (Federació Salut Mental Catalunya). The main role of this Barcelona-based project was taken by Co-Researchers, 32 people with first-hand experience of mental health, or family members. After an Open Call, they actively participated in all phases of the project, including writing microstories of their lived experiences, co-creating a chatbot, promoting it through press interviews and conferences, collectively interpreting the data collected and transforming them into 14 policy recommendations. The project focuses on the mental health social support networks, which are increasingly acknowledged as facilitators of the processes of recovery and improvement of quality of life, as well as a preventive factor in situations of isolation and social exclusion. People with lived experience in mental health and their families claim their importance and effectiveness; nevertheless, scientific research on them is still relatively scarce. This immersive workshop will share with the participants the practices and learnings of CoAct for Mental Health Citizen Social Science project. It is co-facilitated and copresented by two Co-Researchers, people with first-hand experience of mental health and family members and one academic researcher, belonging to the team that promoted the project. Thanks to the hands-on approach of the workshop, the participants will adopt the role of the Co-Researchers and will also be able to envision the successes and the challenges of the project through a horizontal and bidirectional circular dialogue. The goal of this immersive session is to explain and to simulate part of the co-design process. Both non-digital (a research diary) and digital (a chatbot) tools were used. Participants will have the opportunity to experiment with the research diary and use it to write down personal experiences in the form of microstories. Participants will afterwards discover how the CoResearchers microstories were shared with the citizen scientists, in the form of a Telegram chatbot. This hands-on experience will serve as a basis to open-up the discussion. To motivate horizontal and active participation, an innovative format will be used, where the copresenters of the workshop and volunteers among the participants are alternatively asking and answering questions, in a 5-minute time windows. The practices, knowledge, and experiences of all actors of the project will be openly shared and commented, while evidencing that all people are knowledgeable.

69 - The Ethical Review of Citizen Science in Health: what is an appropriate review regime?

Gaston Remmers, Steph Grohmann, Chiara Cardelli, Rhoda Schuling, Kris Bevelander

Room Inspire (DL)

Ethical issues are among the top two issues that need further exploration and development to enable Citizen Science for Health, and are a major differentiator between Citizen Science in the health domain, as compared to other domains (Remmers et al, forthcoming), Cooper et al, 2019). Standard ethical review procedures are often at odds with citizen science projects in the health domain. In the literature, several problems have been put forward. Ethical Review Boards (ERBs) tend to favour certain types of methodology, especially RCT's over other methods, with little appreciation for participatory and gradually evolving methods. ERBs also have difficulty appreciating research in which the researcher is also the researched, and single case subject research in general. In addition, the space for risk assessment by citizens themselves is minimal: i patients don't usually take part in ethical reviewing. At the same time, there is legitimate, ethical concern for participating citizens in Citizen Science health research. Creating a form of ethical appraisal for Citizen Science in health would support the prevention of situations in which citizens gain illegal access to each other's health data , in which citizens nudge or coerce each other in self-experiments that can be potentially damaging, or in which commercial companies push products through citizen science for example (Vayena.et al, 2015) Where to draw the line is a delicate matter however. The ECSA working group CS4H wants to generate arguments and lines of actions to help define this line. The session we aim for is a mix of a workshop and a solution room. After 3 short introductory notes, we will have an interactive dialogue exploring answers to this central question: How would Ethical Review Boards operate that facilitate Citizen Science for Health? We aim, as output of the workshop, for a set of recommendations for ethical review boards that fit Citizen Science in the health domain.

70 - A Patient Standpoint theory for Citizen Science as an example of Iterative Co Design with marginalized, community and health system outsiders

Nancy Marlett

Room TL2187 (TMC)

This workshop uses the co design of a novel standpoint theory to captures the unique nature of the experience of being a patient in complex and hierarchical health systems that rely on the power of access to life and death resources to enforce compliance. Standpoint theory of gender, race, indigeneity, and disability are by nature emancipatory but the power differentials in health care require research models that are pragmatic, non-confrontational and robust to engage not only patients but health professionals and researchers. The co design of this standpoint theory took many years of working with patient populations in and out of health systems to understand the impact of systems and the lack of health centred relationships among patients. The resulting standpoint grid was designed for peer research and as such can be used by individuals, groups of patients and patient programs to understand the complexities of identity and agency in health systems. Themes: The themes focus on • Changing roles of patients in health research from compliance, partnerships in health research, to peer researchers in health research teams. • Disability, indigenous and culture studies as JEDI pioneers of standpoint theory. • Changing focus from deficit, symptoms, dependence and compliance to capacity, assets and expertise in solving main concerns of populations. • Identity and agency as vectors of standpoint theory in health Methods and engagement of participants in the workshop. Participants are engaged in learning about standpoint theory as they identify their personal and professional experiences as patients or working with patients. • The use of Narrative and Salutogenesis (the study of the search for wellness in spite of illness, loss or trauma) as essential frameworks for patient expertise. • Identifying personal and professional experience or interest as part of the evolution of patient roles in health research. This includes beginnings of behavior management, co created adaptive functioning assessments, peer support, peer and patient led research, peer research bridges between academic research and innovation. Using Standpoint theory from personal or professional perspectives. • Once the co design experience is complete, participants work in pairs to tell a story of a health care experience, plot it on the standpoint grid and identify directions they might take to achieve a goal suggested by the standpoint transitions. Benefits: This workshop includes participants in a co design experience related to patient standpoint theory. The theory allows workshop participants to experience the complexity and conflicts inherent in patient experiences within siloed systems. Patient standpoint was designed to enable patient participant co researchers and trained peer researchers to collect and analyze real life stories. It moves from past and present stories to envision future services, technology, policy and relationships that celebrate patient expertise, community options and social innovation and enterprise in community health care futures.

Tuesday, October 31 (15:30-16:30)

Poster session II; 60 minutes (71-93)

Room Atrium (TMC)

71 - Do researchers find it worthwhile engaging the public? Lessons learned from ‘A Healthier Southern Denmark’

Anne Kathrine Overgaard, Thomas Kaarsted

Do researchers find it worthwhile engaging the public? Lessons learned from ‘A Healthier Southern Denmark’ Citizen Science (CS) within Health Sciences appears to be a growing area. Medical and health-related researchers have traditionally seen citizens as patients and to a lesser degree individuals, and at the same time more hospitals have strategies mentioning a humancentered approach. In connection, the pressure on the healthcare sector is growing in Europa due to aging population and increasing pharmaceutical prizes, while the public in general is not included in the prioritization that follows. The CS project ‘A healthier Southern Denmark’ explore citizens willingness to take part in a prioritization of health-related research projects and challenge the researcher toward a more public communication and dialogue with citizens. Five research projects with CS-elements are chosen by a scientific committee and presented to the public by media, and then it is up to the citizens to vote by SMS and thereby prioritize and decide which projects is funded (2 mio. DKR from the Region). While not at traditional CS-project, the project still includes the CS-elements: inclusion, contribution and reciprocity (Golumbic et al., 2017). During the five years run of the project had 52.674 votes and a total reach with +2 mio. interactions in a region with 1,5 million citizens. Based on a survey with the 24 research groups who has participated in ‘A Healthier Southern Denmark’ this poster presents the researchers experience with engaging the public, and their motivation to do so in the future.

Tuesday, October 31 (15:30-16:30) - Poster session II; 60 minutes (71-93)

72 - How to ensure a collaborative priority setting in participatory health research? Reflections on defining events in the initial phase of collaboration.

Elna Leth Pedersen

Background The preliminary phase in participatory health research has been identified as the most critical phase [1]. Particularly, in this phase considerations of power differences and ethical aspects are important for motivating participants and ensuring equitable participation and democratic collaboration. **Aim** This poster discusses some of the ethical considerations and reflections on power-relations in priority setting in the preliminary phase of a Ph.D.-project. The purpose of the Ph.D. is to understand how patients with co-morbidity and chronic illnesses and their relatives perceive communication with healthcare professionals in outpatients' clinics in a Danish hospital. The aim of this poster is to share experiences of critical meetings with patients and relatives, where priority settings such as 'who initiates', for 'what purpose', 'who participates and how' were negotiated. The poster demonstrates how the negotiation led to reflections on power-relations and a more ethical, epistemological and democratic preferable design. **Methods** In a six-month preliminary pre-Ph.D. phase, I met with patients and relatives in different forums. They questioned the meaning and relevance of the research for patients and relatives, expressed the needs for adjustments of language to avoid exclusion, and suggested broadening the perspective of forms of participation to improve stimulation and maintenance of motivation. **Discussion** At the Citizens Science for Health conference, I wish to discuss the ethical considerations in the preliminary phase of research that are necessary to ensure equity in collaboration.

73 - What is the problem with barriers to patient and public involvement in health research? A critical review

Lauge Neimann Rasmussen

It is challenging for researchers and citizens to take part in patient and public involvement. So-called barriers are said to obstruct efficient, enlightening, and ethical collaborations. However, academics rarely define what a barrier is, other than it is standing "in the way" of and obstructing something. Presenting a myriad of barriers (and facilitators) is a little more helpful than a structured brainstorm. We need better ways to grasp what is difficult about patient and public involvement. **Objective** To critically review existing literature about barriers to patient and public involvement and suggest new ways we can understand and talk about the barriers. **Methods** On 27 May 2023, 1,012 articles were identified in the research databases MEDLINE, Embase, CINAHL, and PsycInfo. The articles will be screened and critically reviewed by the author and an interdisciplinary group of health researchers. Our interpretations will be presented to people with diabetes who are invited to comment on and challenge the findings. Their feedback will be incorporated into the review allowing coauthorship as appropriate. **Findings** I expect the review to be completed in time for the Citizen Science for Health Conference and can provide an updated abstract by then. The review findings will include a description of what characterises the literature, conceptual blind spots, and new lines of thinking about barriers to involvement. The latter might include "barriers as metaphors", "barriers as negative variables", and "barriers as researchers' resistance to involvement". The poster will include images that present the findings in an illustrative way.

74 - Exploring the role of experts-by-experience in community health promotion

Samantha Elkhuis, Bente van Aken, Kristina Thompson, Annemarie Wagemakers

Background: In the Netherlands, community health promotion programs for families in vulnerable positions are provided. Working with experts-by-experience, or individuals with lived experiences of vulnerability, has been identified as a way to connect to these families. However, the role that experts-by-experience fill, including the role of citizen scientist, is still evolving and not well-defined. This study aimed to explore the role of experts-by-experience in four Dutch municipalities. **Methods:** Participatory Action Research was conducted with a qualitative, exploratory approach. Research methods were participation in program meetings and working groups of experts-by-experience (n=12), interviews (n=5), and document analysis. Transcripts were analyzed thematically. **Results:** Experts-by-experience were both paid employees and volunteers. Their roles varied, and included: peer supporter, policy advisor, expertise promotor, researcher, initiator of innovation, neighborhood representer, neighborhood connector, and referrer. Experts-by-experience worked at different levels, by either interacting primarily with residents, professionals, or researchers. Most experts-by-experience still had a limited role in science, e.g. by contributing to the development of questionnaires. The experts-by-experience who fulfilled the researcher role shared their experiences of vulnerability, and provided advice and support designing, conducting, and interpreting research activities. This role was experienced as positive, but sometimes also as a burden, as 'you literally always have to be vulnerable and open'. **Conclusions:** Experts-by-experience fill a bridge function between families in vulnerable positions, professionals, and researchers. A challenge is to expand the role experts-by-experience within science. This study offers new insights about the work of experts-by-experience in health promotion, and helps to make their roles more explicit.

75 - Co-designing for inclusion: Lessons from the AutSPACES project

Bastian Greshake Tzovaras, Georgia Aitkenhead, Callum Mole, Helen Duncan, Martin Stoffel, David Llewellyn-Jones, Sophia Batchelor, James Scott, Susanna Fantoni, Kirstie Whitaker

Historically, research on Autism has often been performed on autistic people, rather than with them. With AutSPACES – an open and participatory online citizen science project that focuses on sensory processing in built environments – we are exploring how co-created citizen science can lead to more inclusive and applied research. By combining co-design of research methods; co-leadership for decision making; and using open source philosophies we aim to guarantee the equitable co-ownership of all our outputs.

In our poster we will reflect on the challenges that we have encountered throughout this process that has been going on since 2019 – including the barriers to creating inclusive online communities, technical challenges, and the building relationships between historically distrusting communities. Beyond those challenges we will also share our success stories and how we managed to overcome many of these challenges: through on-going relationship building, providing diverse engagement pathways for contributors and by taking a long-term view on real-world impact rather than focusing on short-term academic impact.

We expect that this sharing of our learned lessons can support and inspire others that aim to develop co-led research efforts with diverse communities and in particular those which typically have been marginalized by academic research to avoid some of the issues we encountered. Furthermore, we hope that we will be able to learn from others that have already tried similar approaches within their own fields or domains, sparking mutual learning.

76 - Open Innovation in Science Impact Lab - Caring Communities for Future

Laura Soyer, Lisa Schlee, Irina Vana

The gradual aging of the population as well as current socio-economic developments are leading to an increasing demand for quality health care and nursing, which poses complex challenges for society and the health care system in particular. The Open Innovation in Science (OIS) Impact Lab “Caring Communities for Future” aims to meet these challenges and support innovative approaches and ideas for addressing community health needs, by improving the cooperation between civil society initiatives, municipal administrations, and professional services that strengthen the quality of life and health in a community.

The OIS Impact Lab, a strategic partnership between the Ludwig Boltzmann Gesellschaft and the Austrian National Public Health Institute, is established as a laboratory to apply Open Innovation in Science to the field of health and community care. The lab funds five transdisciplinary research projects addressing complex challenges at the interface of health promotion, urban and regional development, and social and care sciences. The OIS Impact Lab supports projects striving for the further development and sustainable anchoring of Caring Communities in our societies and involving different actors from research, civil society, and practice.

The LBG Open Innovation in Science Center offers all project participants continuous reflection and networking opportunities as well as training in the areas of transdisciplinary research, participatory methods and collaborative practices with stakeholders from society, science and practice. The cooperation of the LBG Open Innovation in Science Center and the Competence Center Future Health Promotion (Austrian National Public Health Institute/Austrian Health Promotion Fund on behalf of the Austrian Ministry for Social Affairs, Health, Nursing and Consumer Protection) within the framework of the OIS Impact Lab aims to support the knowledge transfer between research projects and innovative municipal practice projects.

77 - Why Citizen Scientists Want to be Involved in Translational Medicine Research in the Fields of Endocrinology and Metabolic Diseases?

Syed Ghulam Sarwar Shah, Yolanda Barrado-Martín, Thomas Marjot, Jeremy Tomlinson, Vasiliki Kiparoglou

Background and objective: There is a dearth of translational health research utilising citizen science approaches notably in the areas of endocrinology and metabolic diseases. We involved citizen scientists in a translational medicine experiment on non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) and a 12-week lifestyle and weight loss intervention. We report the motivations for citizen scientists’ interest in our translational medicine study. Methods: We recruited citizen scientists through various channels. They completed an Expression of Interest (Eoi) form, in which we requested their demographic information and the reasons behind their interest in the study. We used the Voyant Tools to analyse this qualitative data. Findings: Citizen scientists were female (83%), white (50%), older than 50 years (67%), educated to postgraduate level (83%) and either not in employment or retired (83%). The study piqued the interest of citizen scientists for two broad categories of reasons: (1) Personal reasons: having a medical condition relevant to NAFLD themselves or in a family, being interested in lifestyle and weight loss interventions, improving personal health and fitness, being interested in the outcome of the research study, reading about the research conducted at the institution, seeing how research findings are produced, wanting to become a scientist. (2) Altruistic reasons: helping and benefiting individuals with NAFLD, understand health issues better, making contributions to the science, work with the most interesting people, and find solutions to help the societies that are

affected by the condition. Conclusion: Both personal and altruistic interests drive citizen scientists' involvement in translational research for health. Keywords: Citizen science, Translational medicine research, Biomedical research, Public involvement in research, Health research.

78 - Participatory Approaches to change Health Systems: A Systematic Review of Involvement Levels

Jesse David Marinus

Introduction: Addressing health disparities and promoting health and well-being for all, poses significant challenges, particularly for marginalized groups with low socioeconomic status (SES). To tackle these inequities, especially in a time of governmental cutting on welfare spending and increasing care demand due to population aging, it is crucial to re-evaluate the governance structures of health systems. One way is by placing the communities central in the decision making process through participatory approaches. But current studies on participatory research on health systems show different levels of actual involvement of these communities.

Methods: This systematic literature review investigated the actual involvement levels of communities in different parts of participatory research on health systems. A comprehensive search was performed across three electronic databases for relevant studies published in English prior to May 1, 2023. The study selection process adhered to the established PRISMA guidelines. A narrative synthesis approach was used to show the different participatory approaches employed and the levels of community involvement.

Results: A total of 7,511 potentially relevant studies were identified after removing duplicates. The studies that met the inclusion criteria demonstrated a diverse range of participatory approaches implemented in health systems research, such as community-based initiatives, rural appraisals, and participatory action research. These also differentiated overtime and in different regions. When analyzing the studies through the participation ladder, it revealed a wide spectrum of actual community involvement, ranging from a single focus group to comprehensive engagement in each stage of the research process.

Conclusion: This systematic literature review showed that while participatory approaches are about providing ownership of the research to communities, health systems studies using a participatory approach term have a wide range of actual involvement levels. A remaining question is if the use of participatory approaches is not merely a buzzword within academia. To restructure health systems by placing communities central in the decision-making process, it is imperative to shape the research approach in alignment with non-positivist paradigms.

79 - Will cooperating with scientists increase high school students' scientific literacy?

Berit Elisabeth Alving, Mette Fentz Haastrup, Connie Svabo, Katrine Bergkvist Borch, Maiken Westen Holm Svendsen

Aims 1. Engaging high school students. 2. Empowering student's scientific literacy level. 3. Register progressions in scientific literacy. The University Library of Southern Denmark (SDUB) and SDU Citizen Science Knowledge Center is partner in "A Healthier Southern Denmark" project. A high school panel is established in collaboration and co-creation with high schools in the region.

Methods Students from 9 classes and 6 high-schools (ap. 300) participated 2022. An online guide was part of curriculum, and contained documents and videos on health subjects, designs for user-involved studies and participatory democracy. Students interviewed researchers and produced a conference poster. The evaluation on the student's scientific literacy, was a mixed-methods study, containing an online multiple-choice test conducted twice, observations and interviews.

Results A minor progression in scientific literacy level was found and presented in a report in august 2022. In seven out of ten of the questions the average score for all classes were 5,2/10 first time and 5,8/10 in the second. Questions on source criticism had a higher score, as questions with mathematics had a lower score. Observations and interviews showed some progression in students' scientific literacy. Students were engaged in the project, particularly in interviewing scientists, mainly physicians. Students were well prepared and learned critically reading scientific information, and communicating scientific topics, thus became more literate. Projects like this is a core task for SDUB, as it may increase high school students' scientific literacy level.

80 - Ciência + Cidadã program in Portugal – health related citizen science projects

Maria João Leão, Ana Silva, Ana Margarida Almeida, António Gomes da Costa, Céu Claro, Elisabete Brigadeiro, Filipa Grosso, Isabel Gordo, Jocelyne Demengeot, Luís Teixeira, Luísa Peixe, Maria José Amândio, Karina Xavier, Paulo Durão, Pedro Matos Pereira, Renata Ramalho, Sarela Garcia-Santamarina

The Active Citizenship Program - Ciência + Cidadã (C+C) (<https://cienciaMaisCidada.pt>) is an innovative project in Portugal launched in a close partnership between Instituto Gulbenkian de Ciência (IGC), ITQB NOVA and Oeiras Municipality, with the mission to promote: C+C has three main pillars as mission: I. Citizen Science projects, developing scientific research

projects with the involvement and active participation of citizens in close collaboration with researchers II. Co-creation, thinking about science with people and combining education, art and sport III. Public consultation, in decision-making for science through citizen assemblies and other participatory initiatives, in an open dialogue between citizens, scientists and political representatives We are developing two health related citizen science projects within the scope of C+C, namely: I. Citizen Science in a Pioneer Study of Intestinal Microbial Dynamics in Portugal This study aims at the 1st characterization of the dynamics of the human Intestinal Microbiome in Portugal. A temporal study of the intestinal microbiome of 30 families will be carried out, with the voluntary participation of approximately 120 people aged over 5 years. II. Citizen Science project to discover new antibiotics and to map antibiotic resistances in Portugal This project will be carried out in collaboration with the Micromundo@UPorto and inspired by the international citizen science project Tiny Earth. It will involve high school and university students. Citizens of different ages and social backgrounds will be actively involved during the various phases of the research projects.

81 - It's time for researchers to meet Citizen Science! Institutional changes to embed Citizen Science in RPOs: the case of UniSR as an Implementer partner of the European project TIME4CS

Maya Fedeli, Elena Maffia, Federica Prete, Roberto Buccione

Institutional barriers and lack of engagement in research-performing organisations (RPOs) may limit the development and impact of CS initiatives. To overcome these obstacles, the Horizon 2020 TIME4CS project focuses on facilitating the organisational transformation needed to support CS in RPOs. TIME4CS is based on continuous mutual learning between front-runner RPOs, with established support structure and expertise for CS, and implementer RPOs (such as UniSR) that need support in their transformation through tailored roadmaps. The starting point for UniSR's path towards CS was the creation of a de novo research organisation area dedicated to research development, with the mission to implement strategic initiatives to foster UniSR research excellence and to contribute to the internationalization and competitiveness of the University, through the integration of cross-cutting themes and RRI pillars in all research aspects. UniSR was consequently able to devote a multidisciplinary core team to TIME4CS, composed of people with different expertises, including project management, science communication, open science, and impact assessment. After mapping the initial level of awareness of CS of UniSR researchers, a detailed communication plan was defined with initiatives aimed at increasing it, including seminars, newsletters, articles, and a repository of resources on CS. UniSR students and research support officers were also involved in these initiatives. Moreover, the core team is acting as a contact point for all stakeholders interested in CS initiatives and actively participates in ECSA groups. Of note, as a result of the actions triggered by TIME4CS several CS research projects initiatives are now emerging.

82 - Toward Inclusive Approaches in the Design, Development, and Implementation of eHealth: Scoping Review Into the Intellectual Disability Sector

Julia van Calis, Kirsten Bevelander, Anneke van der Crujisen, Geraline Leusink, Jenneken Naaldenberg

Technologies often do not fit the complex needs and living circumstances of people, for example people with a disability. The use of eHealth is more challenging for people with intellectual disabilities (IDs) than for the general population. User involvement approaches have been developed to overcome this mismatch during the design, development, and implementation processes of the technology. In this scoping review, we aimed to identify the inclusive approaches currently used for the design, development, and implementation of eHealth for people with IDs. We reviewed how and in what phases people with IDs and other stakeholders were included in these processes. We used 9 domains identified from the CeHRes roadmap and the NASSS framework to gain insight into these processes. The participatory development, iterative process and technological development and design domains showed inclusive approaches applied at the start of and during the development, whereas only a few approaches involved end users and iterative processes at the end of the process and during implementation. The literature focused primarily on individual use and the external, organizational, and financial contextual preconditions received less attention. However, members of this target group rely on their (social) environment for care and support. Therefore, more attention is needed for these underrepresented domains, and key stakeholders should be included further on in the process to reduce the translational gap that exists between the developed technologies and user needs, capabilities, and context.

83 - Making technology sensitive by identifying profiles of needs and interests of vulnerable care recipients using human-centered design

Hanneke van Heijster, Julia van Calis, Kirsten Bevelander, Christine Liebrecht, Nadine Bol, Marjolijn Antheunis

It is often challenging to find the right care for people with various forms of disabilities and (mental) health issues, such as intellectual disability (ID), Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), mental disorder or a physical disability. Information about medical, psychological, or social care and support is hard to find, complex, and scattered. With the increasing demand for

care for these 'vulnerable care recipients' and the growing shortages of care personnel, innovative solutions should be explored that can positively impact the access to care. In this study, we aim to create 'profiles of needs and interests' of vulnerable care recipients, that serve as a solid basis for technology development for this heterogeneous group. A total of 10 focus groups were performed with care recipients (n=23) and caregivers (n=9 professional and informal). Co-researchers (i.e., vulnerable care recipients) played an important role in the preparation and execution of the focus groups as well as the data analysis. Data was analyzed through thematic content analysis with an inductive-deductive approach. The inclusive research team connected preliminary themes based on the Ford and Nichols' taxonomy of human universal goals (1987), as part of 'vision in design methodology'. Through the analysis of these universal goals, various profiles of needs and interests of vulnerable care recipients will be formulated. These profiles are presented during the Citizen-Science-4-Health Conference. The added value of the methodology used in this study for the development of technology for vulnerable target groups will be discussed.

84 - Associations over time between fatigue, stress, pain, sleep and activities in rheumatoid arthritis: a citizen science and experience sampling study

Ria Wolkorte, Christiane Grünloh, Clementine Ophuis, Lieke Heesink

Introduction People with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) are experts in terms of living with this condition on a daily basis. Using a citizen science approach, we collaborated with people with RA to ensure that the research question matches their interests, is scientifically relevant, and that data collection is feasible. **Methods** The research topic, question and protocol were developed together with people with RA, using a combination of interviews, a survey, and focus groups. Fatigue and its predictive factors were identified as research topic, given its huge impact on everyday life for people with RA. In the subsequent experience sampling study, people with RA reported data on fatigue, stress, pain, sleep, rest, physical and cognitive activities on 21 consecutive days. Data was collected through an online platform and participants were able to see their own data in graphs. Multilevel linear regression modelling was performed to explore associations between stress, pain, sleep, activities and fatigue on consecutive days, between and within individuals. Results of the statistical analyses were discussed with people with RA. Results 63 participants were included (5 drop-outs; adherence = 87.9% for the 58 remaining participants). Results show a relation between fatigue on the one hand, and pain, stress, rest and sleep, but not with activity. **Discussion** This citizen science study provide indications for predictive factors of symptoms of fatigue in RA, which are important for treatment plans and disease management. Furthermore, the study gives an example of a citizen science approach.

85 - Identification of essential behavioral components in m-Health to optimize citizens engagement with a Physical Activity app

Linnea Marie Sjöberg, Tina Dalager

Strong evidence demonstrates that physical activity decreases the risk of more than 35 different disorders. Yet, most adults are physically inactive. Based on the concept of Intelligent Physical Exercise Training (IPET) we have developed the IPET m-Health app, that generates individually tailored training programs based on information on work profile, physical capacity, musculoskeletal pain, and general health. However, to increase engagement and efficacy m-Health app must be underpinned by components targeting behavior. Thus, the aim of the present study is to identify and design behavioral components through co-creation with citizens. The project is ongoing: **Early spring 2023:** A systematic literature search was conducted to identify essential themes within app design for promoting physical activity. Five themes emerged: 1) Personal; 2) Feedback; 3) Social and supportive; 4) Data tracking/security; 5) User-friendliness and motivational features. **Spring 2023:** In total 5 workshops were arranged involving 77 citizens from one Danish University and two Danish hospitals, who one month prior to their workshop gained access to the IPET app to test it. The five workshops were conducted as 'Think Aloud' sessions, where 1) citizens individually wrote down their thoughts on a post-it, 2) arranged post-its within each theme, 3) across all five themes individually ranked post-its in accordance with the importance for continuous use of the IPET app. **Summer 2023:** The IPET app will be refined according to the highest ranks. **Fall 2023:** Approx. 150 employees will pilot test the refined IPET app with the objective to investigate engagement and different health effects.

86 - StomyCraft: a multichannel approach to support ostomy children and their families

Villa G., Caione N., Maculotti D., Villarini A., Contini A., Spina P.R.

Background Ostomy creation results in the loss of an important bodily function and causes physical, psychological, and social changes in the lifestyle. **Aim** To develop a videogame, an ostomy bag cover and a special LEGO® brick, in order to support ostomy children in the adaptation of the new condition. **Methods** Researchers from various backgrounds and non-researchers, including the Italian patient association, family members of ostomy patients, healthcare professionals, stoma care specialists, and game designer built a phygital approach to support the standard educational pathway for children with an ostomy. **Results** The phygital approach is composed by two part: on the physical side the ostomy bag cover and a special LEGO® brick allows patients to have something on which project their condition. They will foster awareness and acceptance

of their new condition, because children can play with their favourite heroes that have an ostomy bag too. On the digital side, after permission, a videogame is developed on the Minecraft® platform adding some special features related to the child with an ostomy. The child makes choices to continue playing: for example, the type of food chosen allows him to acquire more or less strength which allows him to continue playing. The game can also be shared with other children of different languages and cultures because it is universal. While playing, the child increases awareness and confidence in his own abilities, also strengthening knowledge and sharing of experience. Discussion This project allows children and their families to acquire stoma self-care behaviours and improve the quality of life.

87 - How to improve communication using AI and other information communication technologies

Skirmante Bikaitė & Aelita Skaržauskienė

Communication in citizen science projects plays a critical role. It starts by informing the public about the possibility of joining the citizen science projects, then motivating them to participate and tell others about it. Current research (Schiele, Shafer, Burns, Dijkstra, Benneworth and others) shows a disconnect between citizens and science communication. It is often led by top-down communication that only creates more friction between the public and scientists. This research focuses on a possible two-way dialog to inform and inspire the public to join citizen science projects and ways to improve science communication with the help of AI. A few possible communication options will be presented, and the attendees will be invited to participate in the interactive voting session to decide who communicates more efficiently, AI or Humans. Keywords: citizen science, science communication, communication with citizens, AI for science communication.

88 - An emerging Job Chance for individuals on the autism spectrum, deaf and hard of hearing – Digital Revolution needs competent Employees for qualitative Annotation.

Kristina Köck, Dominik Laister

Due to their condition, individuals on the autism spectrum or deaf or hard of hearing people hold considerable strengths and a crucial potential for the labour market. However, their impairment makes them one of the most disadvantaged groups on the market. Workplaces have changed significantly in recent years, with many jobs being enhanced by digitalisation, which is advancing rapidly. Therefore, there is a growing need for employees to train artificial intelligence (AI) systems through annotation tasks. There are few local service providers for annotation activities, and data is often annotated in low-wage countries under inadequate working conditions. Our research project aims to make annotation a job possibility accessible for individuals who are marginalised in the labour market. In collaboration with individuals with ASD, deaf or hard of hearing (peers), their coaches from the job integration project, a team of developers and an expert social management and work assistant, we are aiming to develop a web-based “training station”, which can be shown to interested people and be used to train their annotation skills and assess their interest and suitability for annotation tasks. The expertise of peers is essential for adjusting the “training station” regarding its applicability, understandability, and usability but also for developing a desired framework (e.g., social factors, space, time, light, technology) for annotation activities. Our intertwined departments (Johannes Kepler University and Hospital of St. John of God/training department for people with ASD and deaf or hard of hearing) offer a well-fitting infrastructure for this multidisciplinary and participatory research project.

89 - Co-creating science communication and research with young people about their mental health during the COVID-19 pandemic

Signe H. Poulsen, Nina Maindal, Kristian D. Oddershede, Mathias Sejerkilde, Stine B. Pedersen, M. Haghju, Emma M. Sinclair, Anne Harrits, Ulrik B. Kirk, Jacob F. Sherson, Gitte Kragh

During the COVID-19 lockdown, many young individuals faced significant mental health challenges as their daily lives underwent radical changes. They were confined to their homes and deprived of regular social activities. In the project "Giving Young People a Voice," we took the initiative to engage young individuals in two-way science communication regarding their mental health, as well as co-creation of coping strategies to empower them. Furthermore, we engaged five of the young people as co-researchers and workshop facilitators. Through three iterative and participatory workshops we actively involved more than 150 (16-20 y/o) young individuals in a cocreative process. The initial workshop focused on the challenges and benefits the young people experienced during the COVID-19 lockdown. In the following workshop, a group of young individuals undertook the task of analyzing these reflections. In the third workshop, a separate group of young participants effectively translated the synthesized reflections into actionable recommendations or advice. Finally, the collaboration was documented by a mixed method approach containing both interviews, observations, and a questionnaire. Results demonstrated value creation for all participants and provided valuable insights for enhancing two-way science communication and co-creation. We propose that involving young co-researchers can be an effective approach to engaging other young people in research through peer-to-peer communication and fostering meaningful participation for all.

90 - The role of body image of adolescents in their social media use – a photovoice study

Felder, A., Ganahl, K., Bernhard, A., Hämmerle, R.

Background: In the last decade the use of social media has evolved largely. Especially adolescents are spending an increasing amount of their time online, scrolling through a great number of images, i.e. body images. Often body images are displayed that represent unrealistic and unhealthy beauty ideals, which can lead to mental health problems in young people. However, social media is a big part of many teens' life, which makes body image on social media an important concern for young people as we can see in movements like "body positivity" or "body neutrality" and in many studies that demonstrate that social media triggers teens to dislike their body. Therefore social media can play a great role in health promotion, especially for adolescents.

Methods: Teenagers living in Austria take part as peer-researchers in a photovoice program which started in May 2023. This participatory research process enables adolescents to show visually and verbally how social media affects their body image in daily life. In two workshops the photos and social media material are discussed and analysed using the SHOWeD Method. In the results workshop the data (photos, links and quotes) are displayed using a multi-touch-table and categorized. The touch-table is also used when presenting the results to stakeholders. In a final step the obtained data is analysed by the researcher team. This photovoice project is designed as participatory project which also includes the collaboration of co-researchers throughout the whole process.

Conclusions: The participatory research process facilitates a deeper understanding for the problems and needs of adolescents regarding their body image in their social media world and encourages empowerment and awareness. Further presentation of generated data to decision-makers allows that the voice of young people is heard. Finally, the results of this photovoice program build a foundation for the implementation of health promotion programs for young people in Austria.

91 - AChild – Austrian Children with Hearing Impairment – A participatory research design

Magdalena Dall, Daiva Müllegger, Daniel Holzinger, Johannes Fellingner

The AChild study investigates child and family outcomes over the pre-school period (from birth to 5 ½ years) in a total population sample of children who are deaf or hard of hearing in Austria. The longitudinal study, which started in 2020 lasts for five years and has a focus on the identification of malleable variables. The study team includes pediatricians, linguists, speech-language therapists and psychologists. Data is collected via parent reports as well as direct assessments. Both the diagnostics as well as the intervention is done within the same department of a hospital and almost all of the study team members are employed by the hospital as well as the research institute for developmental medicine. Additionally, the study is set up in a participatory research design, with a parent-peer as part of the research team. In collaboration with researchers, clinical linguists, physicians and the parent-peer the study design was conceptualized, and is now implemented. One important aspect before the start of the study was the selection and testing of the parent questionnaires and during the study, the constant and ongoing interaction with parents and direct incorporation of feedback to the study team.

92 - The Co-Researchers journey in CoAct for Mental Health

Assumpta Mateu, Amanda Figueras, Isabelle Bonhore

This graphic document is a testimony of the Co-Researchers' contribution to CoAct for Mental Health over a long and still unfinished journey, from 2020 to 2022. Co-Researchers, people with mental health problems and their families, have been the main actors of this research, as in-the-field competent experts. The research involved launching a chatbot in Telegram where anyone can listen to their lived experiences and react to them. CoResearchers have been involved in the interpretation of the data collected and drew conclusions to make political recommendations and support specific demands. CoAct for Mental Health is part of CoAct (Co-designing Citizen Social Science for Collective Action), a project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 873048. CoAct understands Citizen Social Science as participatory research co-designed and directly driven by citizen groups sharing a social concern. We expect to upscale this project at a more global level and to replicate it to other social pressing issues. This storytelling document has been done based on the technique of graphic reporting and represent an innovative way to disseminate citizen science for health results. The graphic recording reports Co-Researchers lived stories collected with interview performed by the graphic artist Verity Harrison. In parallel, the general timeline of the project is represented, from the Open Call to recruit Co-Researchers to the final assembly where the final policy recommendations were presented. The posters' contents will be explained by two of the CoResearchers that participated to the project and one member of the academic team.

A flipbook version is available online: <https://heyzine.com/flipbook/bef4285099.html#page/1>.

93 - REIS: A Citizen Science journey for and with people with rheumatic conditions

Kirsten van Mierle, Eline te Braake, Rita Schriemer, Clementine Ophuis, Valérie Bodelier, Christiane Grünloh, Ria Wolkorte

REIS stands for Reuma en Ik – Self-management and is a project to investigate self-management strategies that people with a rheumatic condition apply. Aim is to provide an overview to inspire others, inform healthcare professionals, and start new empiric research. This project is completely set up and carried out with people diagnosed with a rheumatic condition. REIS is a Dutch word and translates to 'journey'. The poster will visualize the journey we had so far when working together with people with a rheumatic condition shaping a research study. Problem space: A lot of research is being done in relation to rheumatic conditions that focus mainly on the medical perspective. Less is known about what people do themselves to cope with their chronic condition. Unfortunately, there is currently no overview available of which strategies exist, for which phase/for whom it is useful and how people with a rheumatic condition experienced this. We are changing that by conducting a survey to make an inventory of self-management strategies, their experiences (positive/negative) and barriers and facilitators related to these strategies. People with rheumatic conditions and researchers conducted this study in the following phases: 1 Is this research relevant? 2 What does self-management mean? 3 How should the questionnaire look like? 4 Is the questionnaire understandable? 5 Data collection 6 How would you interpret the results? 7 Dissemination of the results Further we will summarize the lessons learned shaping the study together.